

The Holocaust of Jewish Greeks and Jews of Thessaloniki:
Italian truncated and selective Humanity,
Spanish adaptable Citizenship

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Talk and Presentation at the International Scientific Conference

***Diplomacy and the Deportation
of Jews in 1943***

*The goal is to identify and investigate interstate relation that affected
the deportation of Jews from the Southern Balkans and other countries*

Tuesday, January 27, 2015, Skopje
at the Ministry of Foreign Affairs

Co-organizers:

Ministry of Foreign Affairs, Skopje

Diplomatic Club – Skopje

Memorial Center of the Holocaust, Skopje

Institute of National History, Skopje

International Holocaust Remembrance Alliance

Full paper with citations, published in the 2016 Proceedings,
is attached bellow, with link to Power Point Presentation &
the plain text with no citations.

It includes [Update and Addenda](#) (September 2017)
and link to full [Proceedings](#) (end 2016)

(Update September 2017)

Diplomacy and the deportation of Jews in 1943

**Diplomatic Club, Skopje
International Holocaust
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**The Holocaust of Jewish Greeks
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**Paul Isaac Hagouel, Ph.D.
Skopje, Thursday January 27th, 2015**

Thessaloniki
1863, Josef Székely

Salonik.
(Sofianisch)

{<http://www.bildarchivaustria.at>}

1

Link to download the Power Point Presentation:

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/0B9Aca9qaK9sTMXZ3ay1rSmw2RG8/view?usp=sharing>

Update and Addenda September 2017

37 — Brevetto di concessione della Medaglia di Bronzo al Valor Militare alla Bandiera dell'Arma del Genio. (Fronte albano-greco, 28 ottobre 1940)

35 — Brevetto di concessione della Medaglia di Bronzo al Valor Militare al III Battaglione Misto Genio «Julia». (Fronte greco, 5 novembre 1940-23 aprile 1941)

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The Holocaust of Jewish Greeks and Jews of Thessaloniki:
Italian truncated and selective Humanity,
Spanish adaptable Citizenship ¹

Paul Isaac Hagouel, Ph.D. ²

Abstract

The role that Italy played in the Holocaust of the Jews of Thessaloniki has not been documented. Jewish Greeks of Thessaloniki and other nearby locales did not benefit either by Italian or Spanish Diplomacy and the Diplomats. The unfortunate indirect role that Italy played in the Annihilation of Jewish Greeks will be demonstrated. The adaptability, along with the fortunes of war, and, consequently, its interpretation at will by the Spanish Administration, of the Spanish Citizenship (its rights and privileges) of Jewish Thessalonikians is also demonstrated. It is regrettable that the self-evident and obvious duty of a Country – State to protect its own citizens had to be transubstantiated into and elevated to the realm of Humanity and Saving and Rescue.

In the last decade a surge in interest on Holocaust History and Studies worldwide, as well as the maturity of the International Holocaust Remembrance Alliance³ and its impact on the academic, educational and museums and memorials fields, has produced a corpus of works dealing with many aspects pertinent to the Holocaust. One very noble component is the Rescue of Jews in peril of annihilation during those dark years. Diplomats of various countries played a role in the rescue, some in direct conflict and contrary to the guidelines of their superiors and, many, far exceeding their competence and mandate that entailed personal risk and danger. Events that relate to rescue actions by Spanish Diplomats in Athens and Italian ones in Thessaloniki concerning the Jews of Thessaloniki have been documented albeit lacking in detail, especially for Italy. Italy was an aggressor and perpetrator of crimes, so how can one talk, at the same instance, about Italian humanity? And what sort of

¹ Paper presented at the International Conference organized by the Diplomatic Club, Skopje and titled *Diplomacy and the deportation of Jews in 1943*

Note: There is an accompanying power point presentation. The URL link is:
https://www.dropbox.com/s/e60ptjelgz032jx/Hagouel_Jews_Spain_Italy_Skopje_20150127_fin2res_ppt?dl=0 The presentation elaborates on the paper.

² Paul Isaac Hagouel, 11 Chrysostomou Smyrnis Street, GR-54622, Thessaloniki, Greece, E-mail: hagouel@eecs.berkeley.edu, URL: independent.academia.edu/PaulIsaacHagouel +30 23102070886, mobile +30 6974389086

³ www.holocaustremembrance.com (20150125)

citizenship was the Spanish one held by a number of Jews, permanent residents of Thessaloniki, that forbade its holder to enter and take up residence in that same State?

In a previous work of mine⁴ I gave the definition of Holocaust where I noted, in particular, that the term Holocaust incorporates all the primal causes, *causae causans*, irrespective of how far back we have to look and trace the past. Any actions or failures to react of any individual, group, society and/or states which tolerate or, worse, kindle activities that may lead to other Holocausts, not necessarily of Jews, are also included in the definition. Consequently we have to trace how Greece found itself occupied by the Deutsches [German] Reich, the Kingdom of Italy and the Kingdom of Bulgaria in the first place and, thus, the Jews found themselves in this dire predicament with the horrendous outcome and end.

Greece had declared its neutrality early on when the clouds of the impending war were gathering all over Europe. Unfortunately the Head of the Government of the Kingdom of Italy Benito Mussolini⁵ had grandiose ambitions about a new Italian Empire in the Mediterranean. Italy tried to provoke Greece with the torpedoing of the cruiser Elli on August 15, 1940⁶. Even though the identity of the perpetrator was correctly presumed (markings on a stray torpedo that hit the breakwater jetty), the Greek Government restrained itself. But, then, Mussolini started getting very restive since he yearned desperately to “match” the war campaign successes and conquests of his ally Hitler. Documents⁷ prove that, even if he was not preparing for a campaign

⁴ Paul Isaac Hagouel, *Balkan Jews in the 21st Century, Bridge to Friendship and Understanding (The Holocaust in the Southern Balkans)*, Full paper to be published at the Conference Proceedings of the Scientific Forum 70 years from the deportation of Jews from Skopje, Bitola & Štip, March 12, 2013, at the Academy of Sciences and Arts, Skopje, Co-organizers: Academy of Sciences and Arts, Institute of National History, Holocaust Fund

https://www.dropbox.com/s/l4ofsk511nt3t82/Hagouel_Holocaust_in_the_Balkans_Skopje_March_12_2013_f-libre_.pdf?dl=0 (20150125)

https://www.academia.edu/3683003/The_Holocaust_in_the_Southern_Balkans_Balkan_Jews_in_the_21st_Century_Bridge_to_Friendship_and_Understanding (20150125)

⁵ David I. Kertzer, *The Pope and Mussolini : The secret history of Pius XI and the rise of Fascism in Europe*, Random House, 2014, New York

⁶ <http://www.logiastarata.gr/2014/08/15-1940.html> (20150125)

⁷ *L' Agression de l'Italie contre La Grèce, Documents Diplomatiques*, Ministère Royal des Affaires Étrangères, 144 pages, 1940, Athènes, ioannismetaxas.gr/AggressionItalienneIndex.pdf (20150125)

against Greece many months in advance, he was considering and planning for it a long time ago. The Reich not only knew about this but was also proactively “advising” and recommending to the Greek Government to come to an agreement with and cede to any eventual demands by their ally Italy who considered the Mediterranean as its sphere of interest and thus [the Reich] was not interested!⁸

With the benefit of hindsight and interpretative synthesis of the facts [correlation of data] I deduce that if Italy hadn't attacked Greece (and without any provocation!) and Greece wouldn't have beaten her back, then Hitler would not have been compelled to come to her rescue and would not have invaded and occupied Greece. At 3:00 AM in the morning of October 28, 1940, the Italian Minister to Greece, Emanuele Grazzi, handed an ultimatum to Prime Minister Metaxas demanding free passage of Italian Troops⁹. Metaxas replied with a No and war was de facto declared and hostilities started at the Albanian – Greek frontier. More than 11000 Jewish Greek soldiers were amongst the Greek troops that took part in the campaign, including my father Leon, a Lance Corporal. Greeks dealt the first defeat to an Axis power. Mussolini was humiliated.^{10 11} Understandably Greece invited Britain to assist and British troops landed in Greece.¹² Hitler used this as an additional pretext and on April 6th, 1941

⁸ Auswärtiges Amt, 1939/41 Nr.7, *Dokumente zum Konflikt mit Jugoslawien und Griechenland*, Siebtes Weißbuch der Deutschen Regierung, Archiv Edition. Das Buch dient dokumentarischen und wissenschaftlichen Zwecken, die Auswahl der Dokumente findet nicht die ungeteilte Zustimmung des Verlags. Reihe Kriegsursachenforschung, Band 8, Faksimile der vom Auswärtigen Amt der Deutschen Regierung herausgegebenen Originalausgabe, wie sie 1941 in Berlin gedruckt wurde. 200 pages Page 193, Nr. 137, *Sonnleiter, Fuschl, den 27. August 1940, Aufzeichnung über den Empfang Griechischen Gesandten in Berlin durch den des Reichsminister des Auswärtigen von Ribbentrop am 26. August 1940 In Fuschl*
Also in Greek: *Auswärtiges Amt, 1939/41 Nr.7, Επίσημα Έγγραφα επί της ρήξεως με την Γιουγκοσλαβίαν και την Ελλάδα*, 223 pages, 1941, Βερολίνον, Berlin

⁹ Ibid. 7, pages 134 & 134

¹⁰ MACGREGOR KNOX, *MUSSOLINI UNLEASHED, 1939-1941: Politics and Strategy in Fascist Italy's Last War*, Cambridge University Press, 2004, London [Chapter 5, The Attack on Greece, pages 189-230]

¹¹ Edwin Packer, *Italian Fiasco, the Attack on Greece*, pages 256-272
Olivia Manning, *The Greeks at War, Greece, October/December 1940*, pages 273-275
[History of the Second World War-Part10](#), Editors Sir Basil Liddell Hart & Barrie Pitt, Marshall Cavendish USA Ltd., 1973

¹² Sheila Lawlor, *Churchill and the politics of War, 1940-1941*, Cambridge University Press, 2006, New York [Part 3, The Greek Decision (January to March 1941), pages 165-259]

invaded Greece from Bulgaria, an Axis ally. Thessaloniki was occupied on April 9th, 1941.

The conqueror divided Greece into three occupation zones: The Italian one comprising most of continental Greece and many islands, the Bulgarian one comprising Eastern Macedonia and Thrace except the border zone with Turkey, and the German one with the rest of the territory which included also Thessaloniki and its vicinity.

Before we proceed, the term Jew in Greece should be clarified¹³. From the first ever temporary Constitution of Epidavros in 1822¹⁴, the 3d Protocol of the Treaties of London in 1830¹⁵, and with all successive Constitutions to this day, Greece was

¹³ Paul Isaac Hagouel, *The Jews of Thessaloniki: Legacies of the Past, Shaping of Traditions, Challenges for the Future*, Invited Talk and Presentation at Fakirleri Koruma Derneği, November 9, 2014, İstanbul
https://www.dropbox.com/s/mus2eg5zrhz02i4/Hagouel_Istanbul_The_Jews_of_Thessaloniki_20141109_full_pages-libre.pdf?dl=0

Paul Isaac Hagouel, *History of the Jews of Thessaloniki: from Jews to Hellenes, from Antiquity to Modern Times*, Proceedings (to be published) of the International Conference Jews History, Tradition, Culture, Language & Religion. CELEBRATING 70 YEARS SINCE THE RENEWAL OF THE WORK OF THE JEWSIH COMMUNITY, SKOPJE, AFTER THE SECOND WORLD WAR (1944-2014), Thursday, December 18, 2014, Academy of Sciences and Arts, Skopje, Co-organizers: Jewish Community, Academy of Sciences and Arts, Institute of National History, Skopje
https://www.dropbox.com/s/72gonlyhrn04i8h/Hagouel_Skopje_The_Jews_of_Thessaloniki_20141218_ff2-libre.pdf?dl=0

¹⁴ <http://norfid.files.wordpress.com/2010/11/nomos-epidaurou-proswrion-politeumaths-ellados-b-e8nikh-suneleusis-astros-1823.pdf> (20150125)

¹⁵ *A _ Papers relative to the Affairs of Greece, Protocols of Conferences Held in London*, House of Commons, 1830, 340 pages, London
page 316

The London Conferences 1830 No. 25.

PROTOCOL, No. 3, of the Conference held at the Foreign Office on the 3rd of February, 1830.

Present: The Plenipotentiaries of Great Britain; France; and Russia.

...

The Plenipotentiaries of Great Britain and Russia appreciated the justice of this demand; and it was decided that the Catholic religion should enjoy in the new State the free and public exercise of its worship, that its property should be guaranteed to it, that its bishops should be maintained in the integrity of the functions, rights, and privileges, which they have enjoyed under the protection of the Kings of France, and that, lastly, agreeably to the same principle, the properties belonging to the ancient French Missions, or French Establishments, shall be recognized and respected.

The Plenipotentiaries of the three Allied Courts being desirous moreover of giving

founded as a State recognizing only Hellenes and no minorities. All religions were/are tolerated and all were/are fully emancipated. All Hellenes have Civil Rights, there exist no Group Rights. After the conclusion of the Balkan Wars^{16 17}, Thessaloniki became officially Greek with the 1913 Treaty of Bucharest¹⁸. All its inhabitants, Christians, Muslims, Jews, Armenians etc became Greek – Hellenes with the 1913 Treaty of Athens.¹⁹

Hence, on April 9th, 1941, the Jewish population of Thessaloniki is comprised, overwhelmingly, by Jewish Greeks. There exist around five hundred Jewish Spaniards, permanent residents of Thessaloniki and a lesser number of Jewish Italians [note that in the Italian Diplomatic Correspondence they are referred as *Israeliti Italiani* i.e. *Italian Jews*], also permanent residents of Thessaloniki, and a minute number of Jews of various other nationalities. It is more than safe to claim that the totality were of Sephardic origin and spoke Ladino [Judeo Espagnol].

to Greece a new proof of the benevolent anxiety of their Sovereigns respecting it, and of preserving that country from the calamities which the rivalry of the religions therein professed might excite, agreed that all the subjects of the new State, whatever may be their religion, shall be admissible to all public employments, functions, and honours, and be treated on the footing of a perfect equality, without regard to difference of creed, in all their relations, religious, civil, or political.

16 JACOB GOULD SCHURMAN, *The Balkan Wars 1912-1923*, 3ed, The Floating Press, 2008, Auckland, New Zealand

Richard C. Hall, *The Balkan Wars 1912-1923 Prelude to the First World War*, Routledge Taylor & Francis, 2000, New York

17 Note: With the end of the Balkan wars in 1913, 4 interrelated Peace Treaties were signed. These were the Treaty of London, the Treaty of Bucharest, the Treaty of Athens and the Treaty of Constantinople. The following URL link gives the full text of all Treaties: https://www.dropbox.com/s/2yk8dkz91lnfsp/Various%20Treaties_%282013%29_distr_p.pdf

18 *Treaty of Bucharest*:

<https://www.dropbox.com/s/j7uzxyrre3ychcc/1913-08-10-TraitedeBucarest.pdf?dl=0>
Ratification of Bucharest Treaty of 28Jul-10August 1913, *Government Gazette of the Kingdom of Greece*, Fascicle A, Nr. 217, 28 October 1913, Athens, www.et.gr (20150125)

Note: All Laws, Directives, Presidential decrees etc are freely accessible (Article 7, Law 3861/2010 for Transparency in Public Administration) at the Website of the Hellenic Government Gazette: www.et.gr.

19 *Ratification of the Peace Treaty* (in Greek & French), *Government Gazette of the Kingdom of Greece*, Issue A, Number. 229, 14 November 1913, Athens, www.et.gr [Note: It is the 1913 Treaty of Athens]

The fate of the Jewish Greeks of Thessaloniki as well as of the Bulgarian occupied territories and of the former Italian occupied ones after Italy capitulated on September 8, 1943²⁰ was total annihilation in the Death Camps in Poland. A few thousand, who fled and hid or were rescued, survived. Of the 48000 something deported – shipped to Auschwitz – Birkenau from Thessaloniki and surroundings, in the spring on 1943, only 2000 survived the ordeal²¹. The Sephardic Jewish Greeks from Eastern Macedonia and Thrace were also deported and all were annihilated at Treblinka²².

²⁰ Note: After Italy capitulated, all Jewish Italians that were still in Greece (mainly Athens) were, automatically, considered just plain Jews for the German Occupation Authorities and the destiny reserved for them was, if caught, deportation and annihilation at Auschwitz–Birkenau

Danny Bennahmias, private communication & conversation, 1974, Oakland, California

Rebecca Camhi Fromer, *The Holocaust Odyssey of DANIEL BENNAHMIA*, *Sonderkommando*, The University of Alabama Press, 1993, Tuscaloosa & London

²¹ Paul Isaac Hagouel, *The History of the Jews of Thessaloniki & the Holocaust*, 2006, West Chester, Pennsylvania & Thessaloniki (2008)

https://www.dropbox.com/s/ozmj8h58j8v8io5/Hagouel_Thessaloniki_Holocaust_n_n-picture.pdf (in English)

https://www.dropbox.com/s/yttkjrxyq642k9f/Hagouel_Holocaust_WCUPA_2006_show.pps?m (in English)

https://www.dropbox.com/s/i58leisp25s0ras/Hagouel-Hol_USConsulate_2008_color_show.pps?m (in Greek)

Paul Isaac Hagouel, *The History of the Jews of Salonika & the Holocaust – an Exposé*, *Sephardic Horizons* (Editor: Judith Roumani) Volume 3, Issue 3, Fall 2013

<http://www.sephardichorizons.org/Volume3/Issue3/hagouel.html>

https://www.dropbox.com/s/474zcyjv6z9gzqg/%282013%29_in_Sephardic_Horizons_The-History-of-the-Jews-of-Salonika-and-the-Holocaust-An-Expos%C3%A9_f.pdf

²² Ibid. 4

Paul Isaac Hagouel, *Ολοκαύτωμα, Εξόντωση, Μνήμη των Εβραίων Ελλήνων της Θεσσαλονίκης, Ανατολικής Μακεδονίας και Θράκης* [*Holocaust, Annihilation, Memory (Remembrance) of the Jewish Greeks of Thessaloniki, Eastern Macedonia and Thrace*] (full paper in Greek follows the summary in English), to be published in the *Proceedings of the Two-Day Conference 70 Years since the Holocaust.*, Department of Political Sciences, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Saturday, April 6, 2013

https://www.dropbox.com/s/3coi2t702manfnt/_Hagouel_Holocaust_EMacedonia_Thrace_and_Thessaloniki_2013_AUTH_full_post_.pdf?dl=0

Paul Isaac Hagouel, *The Annihilation of Jewish Greeks in Eastern Macedonia and Thrace during WWII: Balkan Particularities, Facts, Memory*, to be published at the *Proceedings of the International Conference, Jews across the Balkans – History, Society and Culture Marking 70 years since the destruction of the Jews of the Balkans (1943-2013)*, October 1, 2013, Skopje at the Academy of Sciences and Arts, Co-organizers: Bar-Ilan University, The Aharon and Rachel Dahan Center for Culture, Society and Education in the Sephardic Heritage, Salti Center for Ladino Studies

https://www.dropbox.com/s/acakpn44x9i98xh/Hagouel_Holocaust_Balkan_Particularities_Skopje_Oct1_2013_f_post_.pdf?dl=0

In 2007, the Italian Embassy in Athens published a volume titled *Ebrei di Salonicco – 1943, I documenti dell’umanità italiana [Hebrews – Jews of Thessaloniki – 1943, the documents of Italian humanity]*.²³ It is regrettable that Ambassador Gianpaolo Scarante, in his salutation of the edition, only mentions the persecution of the Jews during the Nazi (note: neither German nor Italian) occupation and exalts the courageous humanity demonstrated by many Italians in Greece without further elaboration. Bear in mind that during the same chronological period atrocities were committed by the Royal Italian Army against civilians^{24 25 26} and Greeks were literally dying of hunger due to the occupation policies of the Axis allies and of the onerous financial burden of compulsory occupation costs decided and signed by the Reich and the Italian Kingdom in Rome²⁷. It is of interest to put the historic record, regarding Italy and the Jews of Thessaloniki during World War II, in its true context and frame.

²³ *Ebrei di Salonicco, 1943 : I Documenti dell’Umanità Italiana* / a cura di (επιμέλεια) Jannis Chrisafis, Alessandra Coppola, Antonio Ferrari ; traduzioni di (μετάφραση) Flora Molcho = *Εβραίοι της Θεσσαλονίκης : τα ντοκουμέντα της ιταλικής ανθρωπιάς*. Ambasciata d’Italia in Atene, 2007, Athens

²⁴ *Grecia 1943: quei fascisti stile SS. Domenikon come Marzabotto. Oltre 150 uomini fucilati per rappresaglia. Ora un documentario alza il velo sulle stragi del nostro esercito. Occultate*, di Enrico Arosio, L’Espresso, 28 febbraio 2008
<http://espresso.repubblica.it/visioni/cultura/2008/02/28/news/grecia-1943-quei-fascisti-stile-ss-1.7472> (20150125)

²⁵ *MAYPH BIBAOS THS KATOXHΣ, SCHWARZBUCHES DER BESATZUNG*, Zweite ergänzte und korrigierte Ausgabe, Ausschuss der Ausgabe † Petros Antaios, Panagiotis Aronis, Manolis Glesos, Athina Kakolyri, Petros Kouloufakos, Jannis Kyriakakos, Frangiskos Konstantarakis, G.A. Mangakis, Kostas Papajannakis, Haralambos Roupas, Copyright © Athen 2006, Nationalrat für die Entschädigungsforderungen Griechenlands an Deutschland, 128 pages

Lidia Santarelli, *Muted violence: Italian war crimes in occupied Greece*, *Journal of Modern Italian Studies* 9(3) 2004, Routledge _ Taylor & Francis, pages 280–299

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=4KzwYDtnF2s>

Criminali di guerra italiani (20150125)

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=UxIDlIFB08w>

Crimini di guerra italiani in Grecia, 1943 (20150125)

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=eQimOSqRuuk>

La guerra sporca di Mussolini 4/6 (20150125)

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=pWMTFi6sJA>

Mussolini's dirty war (2012 upload) (20150125)

²⁶ M. Cherif Bassiouni, *Crimes Against Humanity, Historical Evolution and Contemporary Application*, Cambridge University Press, 2011, New York [page 715]

²⁷ Σωτήριος Γκοτζαμάνης, *Κατοχικών Δάνειον και Δαπάναι Κατοχής*, 1954, Θεσσαλονίκη, pp. 23, 24
Sotirios Gotzamanis, *Occupation Loan and Occupation Expenses*, 1954, Thessaloniki (in Greek)

Even though Italy was an aggressor and occupier of Greece, she was never prosecuted nor indicted in the Nuremberg trial²⁸. But Italy was also a perpetrator of crimes of war and crimes against humanity²⁹. Italy was a de facto dictatorship tolerated by the King and there existed a benign relationship between the Italian State and the Vatican. Italy had already committed crimes in Ethiopia and, concerning Jews, passed Anti-Judaic Laws starting in 1938³⁰, which were not even rescinded during the brief period of the Badoglio Administration till the capitulation.³¹ Furthermore, all the Italian Diplomats in Greece have not been on record as opposing the regime and what it represented. Continuing to serve can only be construed as tacit approval of the policies of their government³².

Actually, surmising from Italian Diplomatic Documents as presented in both the publication of the Italian Embassy and Daniel Carpi's work titled *Italian Diplomatic Documents of the History of the Holocaust in Greece (1941–1943)*³³ (which, in itself, is another misleading title with respect to its contents), Consuls Guelfo Zamboni and his successor, after June 18, 1943, Giuseppe Michele Mario Castruccio along with Captain Lucillo Merci managed to protect around 350 Jews of Thessaloniki who were either Italians or had a connection with Italy and so they could provide them with temporary Italian citizenship documents. (These events were taking place, during the

²⁸ *Judgment of the international military tribunal for the trial of German major war criminals (with the dissenting opinion of the Soviet member)*, Presented by the Secretary of State for Foreign Affairs to Parliament by Command of his Majesty, House of Commons, [Cmd. 6964] Miscellaneous No. 12 (1946), 30th September 1st October, 1946, Nuremberg, 156 pages, London

Michele Battini, *Sins of Memory: Reflections on the lack of an Italian Nuremberg and the administration of international justice after 1945*, *Journal of Modern Italian Studies* 9(3), pages 349–362, Routledge, Taylor & Francis, 2004, UK

²⁹ Ibid. 24, 25

³⁰ *Le leggi antiebraiche in Italia 1938-1945*, Materiali della Giornata di studio-formazione in occasione del 70° anniversario (Bologna, 6 novembre 2008) a cura di Maria Laura Marescalchi http://www.italia-liberazione.it/ita/doc/leggirazziali_70esimo.pdf (20150125)

³¹ Iael Nidam-Orvieto, *Fascist Italy and the Jews: Myth versus Reality* (20150125) http://www.yadvashem.org/yv/en/holocaust/insights/video/fascist_italy1.asp http://www.yadvashem.org/yv/en/holocaust/insights/video/fascist_italy2.asp

³² Davide Rodogno, *Italiani brava gente? Fascist Italy's Policy Toward the Jews in the Balkans, April 1941–July 1943*, *European History Quarterly*, SAGE Publications, London, Thousand Oaks, ca, and New Delhi, Vol 35(2), 213–240

³³ Daniel Carpi, *Italian Diplomatic Documents of the History of the Holocaust in Greece (1941–1943)*, Tel Aviv University, 1999, Tel Aviv

first half of 1943, when Adolf Eichmann's emissaries were busy deporting all the Jewish Greeks to Auschwitz – Birkenau). As I noted above, those were considered first Jews and then Italians, thus being lesser Italians than the non-Jews. Still, the documents and the numbers reveal, beyond any reasonable doubt, that the Diplomats and the Captain protected, shielded and saved citizens of their Country as was their duty, albeit of Jewish religious descent, and not just any Jew. Granted, they showed zeal in this endeavor; however, they never veered out of their diplomatic competence. They never reached out to Jewish Hellenes to distribute something close to Schutz-Pässe as Swede Raoul Wallenberg and Swiss Carl Lutz³⁴ handed out in the thousands in Budapest to Jewish Hungarians facing imminent fatal danger, a year later, in 1944. And, furthermore, displaying [personal] courage means that we face danger. I do not see or discern that the aforementioned [Italian] diplomats were facing any real danger to their safety with their actions which were completely within their bounds. Still it was an attainment of humanitarian deed even if it was limited in its scope.

In my humble opinion and, in the name of the truth, the title should not be *Hebrews of Thessaloniki*. The correct, and precise one, has to be **Jewish Italians of Thessaloniki**.

³⁵ Furthermore, we read in the Italian Press that Zamboni is portrayed both as the Italian *Schindler*³⁶ and/or the (Giorgio) Perlasca of Thessaloniki [*il Perlasca di Salonicco*].³⁷ How I long-wish that this was really true!

³⁴ *Carl Lutz, the Forgotten Hero* (2013)

http://www.urania-nf.hu/docs/sajto/Mediendossier_ENG_MR_140619_HU_DEF.pdf (20150125)

³⁵ Pier Cesare Ioly Zorattini, Michele Luzzati, Michele Sarfatti (a cura di), *Studi sul mondo sefardita in memoria di Aron Leoni, Olschki, L'evacuazione nel 1943 da Salonicco degli ultimi ebrei italiani e degli ebrei italiani 'provvisori': contesto, questioni e numeri*, Firenze 2012, pp. 251-276

<http://www.michelesarfatti.it/testi-online/12-levacuazione-nel-1943-da-salonicco-degli-ultimi-ebrei-italiani-e-degli-ebrei-italiani-provvisori:-contesto,-questioni-e-numeri/> (20150125)

³⁶ *Guelfo Zamboni, lo schindler di salonicco*, *La Repubblica*, 25 Settembre 2008, <http://ricerca.repubblica.it/repubblica/archivio/repubblica/2008/09/25/lo-schindler-di-salonicco.html> (20150125)

³⁷ *LA BUROCRAZIA AL SERVIZIO DEL BENE, Zamboni, il Perlasca di Salonicco, Dalla Grecia una onorificenza ai rappresentanti d'Italia per l'impegno contro le deportazioni degli ebrei*, *Corriere Della Sera*, 4 February, 2008 http://www.corriere.it/spettacoli/08_febbraio_04/ebrei_salonicco_zamboni_dc07bdb0-d2f2-11dc-8916-0003ba99c667.shtml (20150125)

And it did not – does not do justice to Democratic Post War Italy that the Italian Ministry of Defense conferred, in 1948, the Bronze Medal for valor (sic) to the Flag of the Corps of Engineers (of the Italian Army) respecting the whole “Italian – Greek campaign” at *Fronte Albano – Greco, 28 Ottobre 1940!*³⁸ And, even more damaging, in the year 2012, Ercole Viri, Mayor of Affile, defended a decision by the City Council to use 130000 € of public funds in order to honour convicted war criminal Field Marshal Rodolfo Graziani with a mausoleum and memorial park!³⁹ I yearn to feel confident that the Ancient Greek adage of Demosthenes *προς γαρ το τελευταίον εκβάν έκαστον των πριν υπαρζάντων κρίνεται* (*all previous events are judged according to the last one*) does not hold true in this case.

Italy has to come to terms with some of her rather shameful and ignoble deeds of her past that shade her otherwise postwar stellar record. The cultivation of the notion of the “good” Italian versus the “bad” German and of their depiction as saviors of Jews in general, is being questioned, albeit belatedly and slowly. Historiography always has the last word.

Another special group of non–Greek nationals Jewish inhabitants of Thessaloniki was that of the Spanish nationals, around 500 strong. These were Spanish citizens but they were not allowed to enter Spain automatically. They had to renew their Certificate of Nationality each year (see Figures 1 & 2). The Certificate was issued by the Spanish Consulate of Thessaloniki. As a group they were exempt from the racial laws that were applied to their Jewish Greek coreligionists and fellow Sephardim, i.e. they did not have to wear the Yellow Star or live in the Ghetto⁴⁰. Spain was a neutral country albeit favorably predisposed towards the German Reich

38 *LA BANDIERA DELL'ARMA DEL GENIO*

http://www.iscag.it/FOTO/Foto%20Pres%20Generali/Foto%20Bandiera%20Genio/Band_034.jpg (20150125)

39 *Mayor defends monument to fascist leader convicted of war crimes. An Italian Fascist leader convicted of using poisonous gas against enemy soldiers in Africa was "not a war criminal", said the mayor of the town which has erected a monument in his honour, The Telegraph*, Josephine McKenna, 2 September 2012, Rome
<http://www.telegraph.co.uk/news/worldnews/europe/italy/9515780/Mayor-defends-monument-to-fascist-leader-convicted-of-war-crimes.html> (20150125)

40 Ibid. 21

and the Axis Powers. General Franco was the Leader of the State and the Monarchy had been abolished⁴¹.

As long as Spain was both neutral and friendly towards Germany, Jewish Spaniards were relatively safe. However, with the tempo of the sequence persecutions – deportations accelerating in 1943, the German appetite for more Jews to destine for “Special Treatment [Sonderbehandlung]” increased. Spain’s reluctance to accept large numbers of its undesirable non-resident citizens risked to be construed by the Germans as a «carte blanche» to do as they please with the Jewish Spanish nationals in its fold. Nevertheless, after much bureaucratic deliberation among the pertinent German and Spanish Authorities, the Germans finally deported the Spanish nationals to Bergen-Belsen [August 2, 1943] and housed them in separate barracks. After further deliberations among the Spanish Government and the Germans they were finally freed and allowed to travel to and enter Spain via France (all 367 of them). Their sojourn in Spain was brief, just a few months in Barcelona, and then they were shipped to Casablanca on June 14, 1944⁴². With the assistance of UNRRA they were sent to Palestine. They were finally able to return to Greece after August 9, 1945^{43 44}. All these events are documented via the Certificates of Nationality and the Family (couple) Spanish Passport of David Jacob Gattegno and Rachel Gattegno in my possession. (See the Addendum in the end of the paper)

What makes this topic more pressing today is the need to set the record straight as was/is the case of wartime Italy. Starting with year 2008, the first edition of the book by Matilde Morcillo Rosillo and titled *Sebastián de Romero Radigales y los Sefardíes de Grecia (1943 – 1946)* [*S. R Radigales and the Sephardic (Jews) of Greece (1943 –*

41 Stanley G. Payne and Jesús Palacios, *Franco: A Personal and Political Biography*, The University of Wisconsin Press, 2014, Madison

42 Michael Molho, *In Memoriam Hommage Aux Victimes Juives des Nazis en Grèce*, Communauté Israelite de Thessalonique, Seconde édition revue et augmentée par Joseph Nehama, [printed] 1988, Thessalonique, pp. 111–114

43 Haim Avni, *Spanish Nationals in Greece and their fate during the Holocaust*, Yad Vashem Studies on the European Jewish Catastrophe and Resistance, VIII, Livia Rothkirchen, Editor, Yad Vashem, 1970, Jerusalem

44 Bernd Rother, *Spanish Attempts to Rescue Jews from the Holocaust: Lost Opportunities*, Mediterranean Historical Review, Vol. 17, Issue 2, pp. 47–68, Frank Cass, December 2002, London

1946)] is published⁴⁵. The editor is Casa Sefarad Israel, Madrid. The cover shows people wearing the Yellow Star of David and all pages of the book carry this Holocaust ubiquitous symbol. Yet, Jewish Spaniards were exempt in being marked. In the Preface, the then Spanish Minister of Foreign Affairs Miguel Ángel Moratinos repeats the title and compliments the work of Rosillo for her “*documented exposition of the saga of those Spaniards*”. However, in the Greek translation, the title is translated as *Spain and the Jews of Thessaloniki 1943 – 1950 (!?)* (I am curious; did the Ministry check the translation?). Thus Sephardi is equated to Jew and vice versa.

Guessing from the title one might infer that Radigales was somehow involved with ALL the Sephardi Jews of Greece – I wish he was! Then, in the third page, a more extended title is given that puts the matter in a correct perspective: *Sebastián de Romero Radigales y Los Sefardíes Españoles de Grecia Durante El Holocausto a Través de La Correspondencia Diplomática [Radigales and the Spanish Sephardim of Greece during the Holocaust through Diplomatic Correspondence]*⁴⁶. This secondary title reveals that Radigales was either interested or, most probably, could shield and protect only Sephardic Jews holding the Spanish citizenship and not the rest of the Sephardim (By the way, Greece was also home to non – Sephardic communities such as the oldest **Romaniote** community, numbering almost 2000 souls, at Ioannina (Janina) – of the 1960 deported to Auschwitz in March, 25, 1944, 1850 would never return⁴⁷).

The case of the Jewish Spaniards in Thessaloniki is more peculiar than the one of the Jewish Italians.^{48 49} Spain was neutral; no Anti–Judaic Laws were passed even

⁴⁵ Matilde Morcillo Rosillo, *Sebastián de Romero Radigales y los sefardíes de Grecia (1943-1946)*, Casa Sefarad Israel, © Metáfora Ediciones, 2008, Madrid

⁴⁶ Note that, like Italian, in this case the descriptive adjective is the citizenship – nationality (e.g. Italian, Spanish) and the noun is the Jew (or Sephardi), where, according to constitutional mandates, both should have been talking about Italians or Spaniards (albeit of Jewish descent) and **not** about Jews.

⁴⁷ Rachel Dalven, *The Holocaust in Janina*, Journal of Modern Greek Studies, Volume 2, Number 1, May 1984, pp. 87-103 (Article), Johns Hopkins Univ Press, Baltimore

⁴⁸ Alejandro Baer, *Zur Judenrettung Spanischer Diplomaten: Mythen, Fakten und Erinnerungspolitik*, Proceedings of 3. Internationale Konferenz zur Holocaustforschung Helfer, Retter und Netzwerker des Widerstands, 2011, Berlin

⁴⁹ Bernd Rother, *Franco und die Deutsche Judenverfolgung*, © Oldenbourg 1998, ©Vierteljahrshefte für Zeitgeschichte Jahrgang 46 (1998), Heft 2, Inhaltsverzeichnis:

though Anti-Semitism was existent even among some of Franco's closest advisors and/or associates and collaborators⁵⁰. Hence one would expect that the self evident duty of the Spanish Legations, present in countries occupied by the Reich, would be to do their utmost to protect and shield their citizens from any perceived dangers. And, yet, this obvious obligation was not transubstantiated into proactivity and action. However, if we take into consideration that Franco remained, for his own reasons, both a believer of and a fancier for Hitler to deliver an Axis victory instead of him (Franco) being a reasoner, and that he did not break off diplomatic relations with the Großdeutsches Reich until May 8th, 1945, VE Day,^{51 52 53} then we should not be surprised about the vacillations of Spanish Diplomacy vis à vis its own citizens, albeit of Jewish descent, as well as the peculiar adaptability of the rights and/or privileges of that citizenship to the whims of who knows which advisor or confidant of Franco, in 1943 and 1944.

Again, I emphasize that Radigales, who arrived in Athens on April 1943, like Zamboni, acted within his competence, albeit pressuring his government to take action in repatriating its citizens of Jewish religious descent⁵⁴. He is supposed to have

<http://www.ifz-muenchen.de/heftarchiv.html> , URL: http://www.ifz-muenchen.de/heftarchiv/1998_2.pdf , VfZ-Recherche: <http://vfz.ifz-muenchen.de> , 1998, München (20150125)

50 Wayne H. Bowen, *Spaniards and Nazi Germany, COLLABORATION IN THE NEW ORDER*, University of Missouri Press, 2000, Columbia and London

51 David Wingeate Pike, *Franco and the Axis Stigma*, PALGRAVE MACMILLAN, 2008, Hampshire UK

52 Christian Leitz, *Sympathy for the Devil: Neutral Europe and Nazi Germany in World War II*, NYU Press, 1st Edition, [Chapter 5, *Spain: The Axis Neutral*, page 157], 240 pages, 2001, New York

53 Julius Ruiz, *Fighting the International Conspiracy: The Francoist Persecution of Freemasonry, 1936–1945, Politics, Religion & Ideology*, Routledge, 12:2, 2011, 179-196

54 *¿Documentos robados? Franco y el Holocausto*

¿Fue Francisco Franco un defensor de los Judíos? A través de historiadores y archivos y testimonios de judíos, indagamos sobre lo que hubo de cierto en esta historia. Al finalizar la II Guerra Mundial, la primera ministra de Israel, Golda Meir, y el presidente del Congreso Mundial Judío, Israel Singer, agradecieron a Franco la ayuda prestada durante el Holocausto. Elie Wiesel, Premio Nobel de la Paz, declaró que "España fue, probablemente, el único país de Europa que no devolvió a los judíos". ¿Contribuyó Franco a la salvación de entre 40.000 y 60.000 judíos perseguidos por los nazis, como señalan algunos autores? ¿O fue un mito que se creó ante el aislamiento al que sometió la ONU a España tras la guerra?

Uno de los libros que han servido de base para este documental es *Franco y el Holocausto*, de Bernd Rother. Otros textos al respecto son *Las montañas de la libertad*

stated that, if the Spanish government did nothing to protect its citizens, Spain would incur the wrath of the Allies and not only. If nothing else, he was speaking in logic and realism that also sprang by the obvious change of the fortunes of war against the Axis powers ever since the surrender of Field Marshal Paulus' 6th Army in Stalingrad on February 1st, 1943⁵⁵. Final defeat of the Reich loomed unmistakable.⁵⁶

It seems that the evident imminent collapse of the German Reich a year later (1944) might have made a noticeable difference in compelling, driving and/or nudging governments and/or their envoys to take action. This was most apparent in Budapest. It is there that the daring Italian Giorgio Perlasca⁵⁷, in conjunction with the activities of Diplomat Ángel Sanz-Briz⁵⁸, Head of the Spanish Legation, acted against

(Josep Calvet), Retorno a Sefarad (José Antonio Lisbona) y En un tiempo sin libertad. Semblanza de una Sefarad inhóspita (Jacobo Israel).
Dirección y guion: Yolanda Villaluenga. Histórico de emisiones: 23/03/2014
<http://www.rtve.es/alacarta/videos/archivos-tema/archivos-tema-documentos-robados-franco-holocausto/1686535/> (20150125)

55 A CUARTA PÁGINA

España, el Holocausto y la memoria perdida
La propaganda de Franco hizo creer, con cierto éxito, que su régimen contribuyó a la salvación de miles de judíos. En realidad fichó a 6.000 sefardíes por iniciativa falangista
El País, Félix Santos, 17 NOV 2012
http://elpais.com/elpais/2012/09/12/opinion/1347442531_615522.html (20150125)

⁵⁶ Emilio Sáenz-Francés San Baldomero, "Not to be shown to researchers": *Spanish Foreign Policy towards the Deportation of the Spanish Sephardic Community of Salonica in 1943*, *European migrants, diasporas and indigenous ethnic minorities* / edited by Matjaz Klemencic, Mary N. Harris, (Europe and the wider world_4), © 2009 by CLIOHRES.net, Published by Edizioni Plus-Pisa University Press, 2009, Pisa

⁵⁷ Enrico Deaglio, *La Banalità del Bene: Storia di Giorgio Perlasca*, Feltrinelli editore - Universale Economica Feltrinelli, 1991

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=nBYf-unALow> (20150125)
Giorgio Perlasca, un eroe italiano (in spagnolo), Fondazione Giorgio Perlasca, Published on May 30, 2013, la versione in spagnolo del film
Hero Refused to Turn Away from Persecuted (Giorgio Perlasca), *Los Angeles Times*, 22 November 1990, page U9, Los Angeles

58 *El Angel De Budapest* (2010) - Pelicula Completa En Castellano Budapest, 1944, en plena Segunda Guerra Mundial (1939-1945), Adolf Eichman dirige la deportacion masiva de judios húngaros al campo de exterminio de Auschwitz.

Ángel Sanz-Briz (Zaragoza, 1910-Roma, 1980), un diplomático de la embajada española en Budapest, utilizó todos los medios a su alcance para salvar el mayor número de vidas posible. Para ello, emitió miles de visados y pasaportes que garantizaban la inmunidad de sus portadores, que llegaron a burlar en ocasiones a las autoridades alemanas y a sus colaboradores húngaros.

Su actividad cesó cuando, en diciembre de 1944, le ordenaron regresar a España. Había logrado salvar a casi 5.000 judíos. Desde entonces, se le conoce como "El Ángel de Budapest". Published on Sep 19, 2013, David Barnave

inhumanity. First Ángel Sanz-Briz got authorization from the Spanish Government to grant Spanish citizenship to Sephardim in Budapest based on and applying the 1924 Royal Law for granting citizenship to people Sephardic origin⁵⁹. However, he was not able to find more than 45 Sephardim amongst the hundreds of thousand of Ashkenazim. He was authorized to provide protection, and hence citizenship for up to 200. So the 200 documents were multiplied and the serial numbering was always the same. Perlasca continued the work after Sanz-Briz was ordered to leave Budapest by daringly assuming the role of continuator in the stead of Sanz-Briz. Now imagine what the turn of events could have been for the Sephardim Greeks of Thessaloniki if the Spanish Legation in Athens had also extended such protection.

For completeness I am quoting 2 recent publications: First the joint 2008 bilingual publication of the Spanish Ministry of Foreign Affairs and Casa Sefarad titled *Visas for Freedom – Spanish Diplomats and the Holocaust*.⁶⁰ Pages 40 to 47 of the document in pdf format are devoted to the efforts of Radigales for the repatriation of the Jewish Spaniards. It is interesting to indicate that on page 14 (second page of pdf) of the promotional flyer⁶¹ for the exhibition it states (in Spanish) that Radigales made efforts to repatriate the Sephardim, without distinguishing between the Greek ones, the overwhelming majority, and the Spanish ones, the minute minority.

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=AzubysQ8Dq4> (20150125)

Ángel Sanz briz. el Schindler Español (DOCUMENTAL)

Uploaded on Nov 27, 2011

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=sMsVwSrfyeg> (20150125)

59 José Cohen, *Los sefardíes y la nacionalidad española*, *Libertad Digital*, 23 April 2013, Real Decreto del Directorio Militar de Primo de Rivera, 20 de Diciembre del 1924, for granting the Spanish citizenship to Sephardim who were: antiguos protegidos españoles o descendientes de éstos, y en general individuos pertenecientes a familias de origen español que en alguna ocasión han sido inscritas en Registros españoles y estos elementos hispanos, con sentimientos arraigados de amor a España, por desconocimiento de la ley y por otras causas ajenas a su voluntad de ser españoles, no han logrado obtener nuestra nacionalidad
<http://www.libertaddigital.com/opinion/jose-cohen/los-sefardies-y-la-nacionalidad-espanola-68228/> (20150125)

⁶⁰ *Visados para la libertad, Diplomáticos Españoles ante el Holocausto*, Ministerio de de Asuntos Exteriores y de Cooperación & Casa Sefarad Israel, 2008, Madrid
http://pendientedemigracion.ucm.es/info/dptoants/curriculos/catalogo_visadosDic08.pdf (20150125)

⁶¹ alerto.es/pdfs/alef_06mar.pdf (20150125)

On November 2014, a 44 page publication of the Spanish Ministry of Foreign Affairs (in Spanish) appears titled *MÁS ALLÁ DEL DEBER, La respuesta humanitaria del Servicio Exterior frente al Holocausto* [*Beyond the Call of Duty, Humanitarian response of the Foreign Service to the Holocaust*]⁶². Pages 13 and 14 are dedicated to Radigales and his actions while in Athens.

Italy and Spain today are far removed from their respective pasts. Spain should be complimented for her earnest efforts in the last 20 years to reach out to all its Sephardic descendants via Casa Sefarad and with its biennial World Gathering for Erensyia Sefaradi, and the new Citizenship Law. Italy is, understandably, proud of acts of humanity during the war albeit truncated and selective and carried out by individuals at their own initiative and not as a state policy. Slowly she is coming to terms with her recent history⁶³.

Nevertheless, the best would have been for us not to be here today to commemorate tragic events. I am sure (I hope!) this history will never be repeated.

Thank you

⁶² *MÁS ALLÁ DEL DEBER, La respuesta humanitaria del Servicio Exterior frente al Holocausto*
http://www.exteriores.gob.es/Portal/es/SalaDePrensa/ElMinisterioInforma/Paginas/Noticias/20141126_MINISTERIO1.aspx (20150125)
http://www.exteriores.gob.es/Portal/es/SalaDePrensa/Multimedia/Publicaciones/Documentos/2014_CATALOGOEXPOSICIONMASALLADELDEBER.pdf (20150125)

⁶³ Maria Cristina Villa, *L'Italia non vede, non sente, non parla: Il cinema italiano della deportazione razziale*, Doctoral Dissertation, University of California, Los Angeles, 2006, Los Angeles

Marta Petruszewicz, *The hidden pages of contemporary Italian history: war crimes, war guilt and collective memory*, *Journal of Modern Italian Studies* 9(3) 2004, Routledge _ Taylor & Francis, pages 269–270

Filippo Focardi & Lutz Klinkhammer, *The question of Fascist Italy's war crimes: the construction of a self-acquitting myth (1943 – 1948)*, *Journal of Modern Italian Studies*, 9(3), 2004, Routledge _ Taylor & Francis, pages 330–348

Addendum: David Jacob Gattegno and Rachel Gattegno The Chronicle–Narrative of the Jewish Spaniards of Thessaloniki

We will attempt to visualize their Odyssey by retracing some instances of their lives these three years (1943–1945). This is a virtual journey for us but a very real one for them fraught with rigor and privation and, most of all, the threat of extermination hanging on top of their heads as long as they were in the custody of the Reich. This we achieve by following the story David Jacob Gattegno and Rachel Gattegno using as a temporal and location fixing compass a set of pertinent archival documents:

The couple David Gattegno and Rachel Gattegno (born Frances) hails from a family that lived for centuries in Thessaloniki. David Gattegno owns (owned) a Print Shop that specialized in quality printing. They are both Spanish nationals, permanent residents of Thessaloniki. They renew their Certificates of Nationality annually and the 1941 Certificate of David displays prominently the new Franco era Coat of Arms (see Figure 1). The German Authorities stamp the Certificate with the following word logo: “**BESCHEINIGUNG DER SPANISCHER ANGEHÖRIGKEIT**” i.e. Certificate of Spanish Citizenship (see Figure 1a). Thus Spanish citizens are identified as such by the Occupation Authorities and distinguished from the Jewish Greeks. They are exempt from the race [«Nuremberg»] Laws which are being enforced upon their Greek national brethren starting mid February 1943.

Figure 1: Front of the 1941 Certificate of Nationality of David Gattegno
The Certificate was issued at Thessaloniki by the Spanish Consulate

Figure 1a: Magnification of the German Stamp that adds the German equivalent of the Document Title of Certificate of Spanish Citizenship

We now follow the itinerary of the Jewish Spaniards by «riding» the Passport of the Gattegnos⁶⁴ and some other pertinent documents of the era as a virtual vehicle.

The Germans draw a list of all Spanish nationals of Jewish origin who belong to the Jewish Community of Thessaloniki. The following Figure 3 shows part of the 12 pages 1943 German document listing the Jewish Spaniards of Thessaloniki⁶⁵. I have included only the names of the Gattegnos without loss of generality. Note that in the last column is written when their Spanish Nationality ID was issued (Compare it with Figure 2). Also note the address given (Hr. Smyrni 9). This is my actual business & home address (!) if new numbering is taken into account [current number is 11].

Figure 2: Details of the 1941 Certificate of Nationality of David Gattegno [inside-back]
The Certificate was issued on July 8, 1941. It identifies David Gattegno as a printer
(The Germans has entered Thessaloniki on April 9 of the same year)

The Gattegnos, like the rest of Spanish nationals, are making preparations for the journey to the . . . unknown. They apply for a husband–wife common Passport at the Spanish Legation in Athens. Their Passport is signed by Consul Sebastián de Romero Radigales (whose name

⁶⁴ *Gattegno 1943–1945 Spanish Passport*, Private Archives of Leon Hagouel, (unpublished and unreleased) 2006, Thessaloniki

⁶⁵ Yad–Vashem Archives–YVA, JM.2218, *List of Spanish nationals in Salonika*, 30/04/1943, 12 frames (K213082-K213093), Jerusalem

appears in the historiography of the Jewish Spaniards of Thessaloniki and who will remain for some years as Consul after Liberation) (Figure 6). The Gattegnos write a letter to Paul Frances⁶⁶, Rachel's son from an earlier marriage, who had managed to leave Greece earlier, describing to him their situation and predicament, mentioning among other things that they were allowed to take with them 5000 Swiss Francs. The letter is dated Thursday, May 27, 1943⁶⁷.

Figure 3: German Legation Legal Advisor von Thadden's letter accompanied with the full list all Spanish Nationals of the «Jewish race» (sic) who belong to the Jewish Community of Thessaloniki as of April 30, 1943. Bear in mind that by that date, out of the total 19 convoys to Auschwitz–Birkenau, 13 had already left . . . (Only the Gattegnos are included without loss of generality)

⁶⁶ Personal Note: I am named after Paul Frances. My other name Isaac belongs to one of my father's brothers who, after having suffered during the aforementioned forced slave labor in various localities in Greece, was gassed almost immediately upon arrival at Auschwitz–Birkenau since he was already in pitiful condition

⁶⁷ Private Archives, (unpublished and unreleased)

Figure 4: Page 1 → The Passport was issued by the General Consulate of Spain in Greece

Figure 5 Page 2 → The Passport was issued on May 25, 1943
 Page 3 → Personal Data of the Passport Holders

Figure 6

- Page 4 → Signature by the Consul General of Spain, Sebastian de Romero, May 25, 1943
- Page 5a → Authorization–Permission by the Consulate General of Spain in Athens for the Holders to enter Spain for one time only (!) from the border crossing at Irun [opposite Hendaye France] (July 6, 1943)
- Page 5b → **Entrance** Stamp in Spain (Port–Bou opposite Cerbère France and not Irun), February 10, 1944 [note the 7 months period that has elapsed]

Figure 7

- Page 6 ➔ Authorization – Permission from the Bank of Greece to export foreign currency (2000 Swiss Francs or the equivalent in other foreign banknotes [currencies]), June 7, **1943**. The export permit is valid for 15 days
- Page 6a ➔ Second **Entrance** Stamp in Spain (Port–Bou), February 10, **1944**
- Page 7 ➔ Authorization – Permission from the Bank of Greece to export foreign currency (3000 Swiss Francs or the equivalent in other foreign banknotes [currencies]), June 9, **1943**. The export permit is valid for 15 days

~~Abstrich~~
Abstrich

Saloniki, den 31. Juli 1943.

Die Zahlung der Drachmenbeträge hat insgesamt
Drach. 32.300.000,-
(32 Millionen, Dreihunderttausend Drachmen) ergeben.-

(Stempel: Der Befehlshaber/gen. Wisliceny
der Sicherheits-
polizei u. des SD.) SS-Hauptsturmführer.

~~Abstrich~~
Abstrich Saloniki, den 31. Juli 1943

Devisenzahlung

Name	Nr.	Devisen
David J. Gattegno	263	S. Fr. 30.- 2

Figure 8: Count List [Devisenzählung] of Foreign Currency, gold and jewelry belonging to Jewish Spanish Nationals being deported to Bergen-Belsen seized-confiscated by the German Authorities one day before the departure of the 19th Convoy (destination Bergen-Belsen), July 31, 1943. The person responsible for collecting the valuables and completing the List was Dieter Wisliceny. Note that according to the Authorization-Export Permissions by the Bank of Greece (Passport Pages 6 & 7) David Gattegno was allowed to take out a total of 5000 Swiss Francs with him . . . (Without loss of generality I include only David Gattegno)⁶⁸

Wisliceny claims that David Gattegno deposited only 30 Swiss Francs while (as we know) he had permission to carry and export up to 5000 Francs (Figure 8). The options are the following:

- 1 David Gattegno took only 30 Francs with him.
- 2 David Gattegno was carrying a larger sum but was able to conceal it despite the threat of severe punishment if found.
- 3 Wisliceny, along with the rest of his detachment, profited from the loot and reported altered tallies to the Reich Finanz [Finance] Authorities.

The most obvious correct answer to this multiple choice question is 3. So Wisliceny and the rest of the perpetrators were not only extraordinary murderers but they were also common thieves [as in crooks, bandits & robbers]! So much for the «High»

⁶⁸ Yad-Vashem Archives-YVA, TR3/345, *List of currencies held by Spanish nationals in Salonika, 31/07/1943*, 5 pages, Jerusalem {From Police d' Israël, Quartier General, 8-ème Bureau, Fiche 345}, Jerusalem

principles of National Socialism, the Herrenvolk and, last but not least, the Elite of the Elite, the SS!^{69 70}

Figure 9: A note, dated December 2, 1943, declares that the «Judenaktion» in Thessaloniki resulted in the confiscation of 22300000 Drachmas, 40185 US Dollars and 55345 Swiss Francs, plus what they seized from the Jewish Spanish Nationals

There exists a «gap» in exit and entry Stamps: First of all they were hoarded on a train and deported on August 2, 1944 so there were no «niceties» such as border stampings exiting Greece, entering Yugoslavia, and then the Reich to Bergen-Belsen (remember Austria was the Reich Province of Ostmark). Again there is no exit Stamps from the Reich or entry into a (fully) Occupied France and dumped at the

⁶⁹ Peter Padfield, "Himmler", MJF Books Fine Communications, 1990, New York

⁷⁰ "The SS", By the Editors of Time-Life Books, THE THIRD REICH, Time-Life Books, 1988, Alexandria, Virginia

French–Spanish frontier at Cerbère (Figure 11) for subsequent entry into Spain and final destination, there, Barcelona (Figures 6, 7, 10 & 11)

Figure 10 Page 5 (stamp) → **Entrance Stamp in Spain (Port–Bou), February 10, 1944**
 Page 6 (stamp) → **Second Entrance Stamp in Spain (Port–Bou), February 10, 1944**

Figure 11

- Page 8 → Authorization by the Spanish Consulate General in Athens for the Pass Holders to enter Spain without having to pay any custom duties or levies for the import of their personal belongings due to the fact that they always resided abroad [i.e. in Greece and not Spain] July 6, **1943**
- Page 8a → One orthogonal Spanish Stamp dated February 2, **1944** (?). A faint digit 3 after the digit 2 is discernible in magnification
- Page 8b → A small round Stamp of the Customs of Port–Bou
- Page 9 → French Exit Visa by the Vichy Police at the border town of Cerbère, Région de Montpellier, opposite Spanish Port–Bou, February 10, **1944**. Note the Vichy Coat of Arms on the Stamp

Figure 12

Page 10 → Spanish Stamp, April 4, 1944

Page 11 → Gratis Extension of the validity of the Passport at the Spanish Consulate General in **Palestine** at **Jerusalem**, July 4, 1945

[Note the gap with no Exit or Entrance Stamps from Spain to Casablanca and then on to Palestine, a time period of more than a year]

A New York Times article⁷¹ dated February 17, 1944 reports that “365 Jews Reach Spain”.

The text follows:

MADRID, Feb. 16 (2P)—The Spanish Foreign Legion announced today that 365 Spanish-speaking Jews descended from those expelled from Spain by Queen Isabella and King Ferdinand in 1492 had been brought to Spain after negotiations with Berlin freed them from a German concentration camp at Bergen Belsen. Thousands of these Spanish Jews lived in Salonika and elsewhere in the eastern Mediterranean. They speak a type of Spanish little different from that spoken in the time of Isabella and Ferdinand. A note by the Foreign Ministry said those repatriated expressed their unanimous thanks and satisfaction for the Spanish Government's help in getting them out of the German concentration camp.

⁷¹ 365 Jews Reach Spain, The New York Times, February 17, 1944

Figure 13: Food Ration Card issued to the Gattegnos in Barcelona

Figure 13b: The outside back cover of the Passport was stamped with the note "UNION OF POLISH INMATES" (in Greek after the return)

Figure 14

Page 12 → Entrance Stamp to Greece and Stamp [Timbre] Consular Fees levied at the Port of Piraeus on August 26, 1945 due the lack of Greek Consular attestation [in Jerusalem]
 Inside Back Cover → Various Stamps, February, March & April 1944 [Barcelona Spain]

There exists another gap in exit and entry Stamps: No exit Stamp from Spain to Casablanca exists and neither an entry Stamp to Palestine (at the time under the League of Nations British Mandate). Figure 12 bears the extension of the validity of the Passport issued by the Consulate General of Spain in Palestine and located in Jerusalem. Figure 13 shows a Food Ration Card issued to the Gattegnos in Barcelona. Figure 14 bears the entry Stamp into Greece at the Port of Piraeus on August 26, 1945. Thus this modern Odyssey differs from the Homeric one in the sense that the wish-goal of its unsung heroes was to return to where they had started from. Their Troy and Ithaca was one and the same: Thessaloniki!

Update and Addenda September 2017

37 — Brevetto di concessione della Medaglia di Bronzo al Valor Militare alla Bandiera dell'Arma del Genio. (Fronte albanico-greco, 28 ottobre 1940)

Numero d'Ordine 72367

REPUBBLICA ITALIANA
DIFESA
MINISTERO DELLA GUERRA

Il Capo Provvisorio dello Stato

con Suo Decreto in data del 31 dicembre 1947;
Visto il Regio Decreto n. 1421 in data 11 novembre 1935 e successive modificazioni;
Visto il Regio Decreto n. 23 in data 22 ottobre 1942 n. 1935;
Sulla proposta del Ministro Segretario di Stato per gli Affari della Difesa;
Ha conferito la **Medaglia di Bronzo** al valor militare all'annoso soprassoldo di Lire Trecento annue alla **bandiera dell'Arma del Genio**

"Durante l'intera campagna albanico-greca, in terreni impervi e tra equi più duri, avvedutezza e intelligenza, attività tenace, infaticabile, eccelsa sperticatezza di decisione e di abnegazione e per apparso nella Divisione, agibile con il genio tutto e compiti, combattimenti sui fianchi, e insomma, meriti per aver dato il valore, per favore di coraggio, di opere, di sacrificio: esempio e promozione di gloria sempre susseguenti."

Fronte Albanico-Greco, 28 ottobre 1940.

Il Ministro Segretario di Stato per gli Affari della Difesa rilascia quindi il presente documento per attestare del conferito onorifico distributivo.

Roma, addì 21 Maggio 1948.

Registato alla Corte dei Conti addì 22 febbraio 1948
Registato al Tribunale di Roma addì 27 gennaio 1948

Il Ministro
(firma Forlani)

168000 sul 1000 del 1948 disp. 27 pag. 543

35 — Brevetto di concessione della Medaglia di Bronzo al Valor Militare al III Battaglione Misto Genio «Julia». (Fronte greco, 5 novembre 1940-23 aprile 1941)

Numero d'Ordine 120264

REPUBBLICA ITALIANA
MINISTERO DELLA DIFESA

Il Presidente della Repubblica

con Suo Decreto in data del 9 giugno 1948
Visto il Regio Decreto n. 1421 in data 11 novembre 1935 e successive modificazioni;
Visto il Regio Decreto n. 23 in data 22 ottobre 1942 n. 1935;
Sulla proposta del Ministro Segretario di Stato per gli Affari della Difesa;
Ha conferito la medaglia di **Bronzo** al valor militare all'annuo soprassoldo di Lire Trecento annue alla **Bandiera dell'Arma del Genio** per il III battaglione misto genio della Divisione asprina "Julia"

"Con ardente tenacia e brillante genialità, in sei lunghi mesi di guerra, in altissimi tra loro ostacoli e nelle intemperie di ogni carattere, ha sempre mantenuto i soldati, ha colpito punti e strade, ha progettato operazioni difensive, con ostilità, all'occorrenza a favorire gli alleati da lavoro e guadagnare con gli asprini nel combattimento."

Fronte greco, 5 novembre 1940 - 23 aprile 1941.

Il Ministro Segretario di Stato per gli Affari della Difesa rilascia quindi il presente documento per attestare del conferito onorifico distributivo.

Roma, addì 20 Ottobre 1948

Registato alla Corte dei Conti addì 22 giugno 1948
Registato al Tribunale di Roma addì 27 gennaio 1948

Il Ministro
R. Accardi

168000 sul 1000 del 1948 disp. 24 pag. 2200

Update and Addenda September 2017
The Holocaust of Jewish Greeks and Jews of Thessaloniki:
Italian truncated and selective Humanity,
Spanish adaptable Citizenship

Paul Isaac Hagouel, Ph.D.
paul231011@berkeley.edu

Note

The reasons that dictate the Update and Addenda have to do with the following:

A. Include, for completeness, the Original Royal Decree (as described in citation note No ⁵⁷ of the original text) authorizing Spanish Diplomatic Authorities to confer Spanish Citizenship to persons claiming Spanish ancestry – descent (that designated, in the overwhelming majority, Jews of Sephardic origin)¹.

[Real Decreto del Directorio Militar de Primo de Rivera](#), 20 de Diciembre del 1924, Gaceta de Madrid - Núm. 356, 21 Diciembre 1924, Páginas 1322, 1323 ²

B. Recent contributions and/or updated compilations concerning the comportment of the **Kingdom of Italy – Regno d'Italia** as an aggressor State, Member of the Tripartite Pact (Axis) with the Deutches Reich,

1 José Cohen, *Los sefardíes y la nacionalidad española*, [Libertad Digital](#), 23 April 2013, Real Decreto del Directorio Militar de Primo de Rivera, 20 de Diciembre del 1924, for granting the Spanish citizenship to Sephardim who were: antiguos protegidos españoles o descendientes de éstos, y en general individuos pertenecientes a familias de origen español que en alguna ocasión han sido inscritas en Registros españoles y estos elementos hispanos, con sentimientos arraigados de amor a España, por desconocimiento de la ley y por otras causas ajenas a su voluntad de ser españoles, no han logrado obtener nuestra nacionalidad
<http://www.libertaddigital.com/opinion/jose-cohen/los-sefardies-y-la-nacionalidad-espanola-68228/> (20150125)
<https://drive.google.com/file/d/0B9Aca9qaK9sTZklNcHpWaGxGbEU/view?usp=sharing>

2

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/0B9Aca9qaK9sTekM1UUk4RGVWYTQ/view?usp=sharing>

co – instigator of World War II, perpetrator of War Crimes in occupied territories including Greece [as well as Persecution of Jewish Italians – this, though, is beyond the scope of the Update and Topic of the original paper].

Also the comportment–conduct of the postwar

Repubblica Italiana pertaining to (including but not limited to): **a.** Italy’s refusal to **extradite Italian war** criminals for trial in Greece (as well as to other countries where Italy was an occupier).

b. The insistence that Greece liberates war criminal **Giovanni Ravalli** who was tried and convicted to life imprisonment (which Greece acquiesced to).

c. Last, but not least, the 16 February 1943 massacre at **Domenikon** in Thessaly Central Greece (which came again into the limelight with a lawsuit deposited in Greek court by descendants of victims and, simultaneously, with a new investigation by Italian military prosecutor).

C. The saga of the original citation Note ³⁷ concerning the conferral of Bronze Medal for valor, in 1948, to the Flag of the Corps of Engineers (of the Italian Army) respecting the whole “Italian – Greek campaign” at Fronte Albano – Greco, 28 Ottobre 1940, by the Italian Ministry of Defense. [Actually they, the Italian Ministry of Defense, mean the Italian – Greek Front on Albanian Territory, theater of the aggressive war of the Kingdom of Italy against Greece that started in the 28th of October, 1940]³.

The above **B** & **C** are all, unfortunately, in stark contrast with the postwar image that Italy is steadfastly insisting on portraying, even though Italy was a wartime aggressor state, albeit with a “humanitarian” flair. The reason is simple: Italy has yet to come to terms, fully, with her past. These still tarnish her, otherwise, stellar postwar record.

³ *37 – Brevetto di concessione della Medaglia di Bronzo al Valor Militare alla Bandiera dell'Arma del Genio. (Fronte albano-greco, 28 ottobre 1940)*
<https://drive.google.com/file/d/0B9Aca9qaK9sTMEZXOF1BMlp3Zzg/view?usp=sharing>

A. The original Royal Decree

Authorizing Spanish Diplomatic Authorities to confer Spanish Citizenship to persons claiming Spanish ancestry – descent and seeking protection.

The original Decree had a terminal date of application 31 December 1930 but it has been invoked in special cases beyond that date (*Private Communication by Ambassador Miguel de Lucas, Director of Centro Sefarad-Israel in Madrid – April 2015 – and currently, 2017, Head of the Spanish Delegation to the International Holocaust Remembrance Alliance <https://holocaustremembrance.com/member-countries-spain/delegation-members>)*

1322

21 Diciembre 1924

Gaceta de Madrid.-Núm. 356

PARTE OFICIAL

S. M. el REY Don Alfonso XIII (q. D. g.), S. M. la REINA Doña Victoria Eugenia, S. A. R. el Príncipe de Asturias e Infantes y demás personas de la Augusta Real Familia, continúan sin novedad en su importante salud.

PRESIDENCIA DEL DIRECTORIO MILITAR

EXPOSICION

SEÑOR: Existen en el extranjero, principalmente en las naciones del Oriente y en algunas del Continente americano, antiguos protegidos españoles o descendientes de éstos, y en general individuos pertenecientes a familias de origen español que en alguna ocasión han sido inscritos en Registros españoles, y estos elementos hispanos, con sentimientos arraigados de amor a España, por desconocimiento de la ley y por otras causas ajenas a su voluntad de ser españoles, no han logrado obtener nuestra nacionalidad. Muchos de ellos están en la errónea creencia de que la poseen y de que para su disfrute sólo les falta algún requisito externo que con equivocado empeño solicitan; otros esperan una naturalización en masa de la colectividad de hispanófilos militantes a que pertenecen y son muchos los casos en que esta misma condición de aspirantes a la nacionalidad española les hace encontrarse con ninguna.

Si bien es cierto que la Constitución y el Código civil indican la manera de adquirir la condición de español y existen para formular las peticiones correspondientes, normas adecuadas en derecho, las dificultades que ofrecen éstas para esa categoría de individuos han sido en la práctica insuperables, agravando por esto y con transcurso del tiempo su situación, verdaderamente anómala.

Por esto, el Directorio Militar, investido de los poderes que el Real decreto de 15 de Septiembre del año próximo pasado le otorgó, ha debido ocuparse de remediar este estado de cosas, no tan sólo para atender reiteradas súplicas de quienes aparecen ante los Gobiernos extranjeros en la condición de cuasi naturalizados, y no podrían permanecer indefinidamente en esta situación incómoda, sino ante la consideración patriótica de

que esos elementos son en general conocedores de nuestro idioma y han de resultar propicios mediante la naturalización a difundirlos en beneficio de nuestras relaciones culturales en países lejanos en los cuales forman colonias que pueden ser de verdadera utilidad para España.

No siendo posible atender la petición de naturalización por colectividades, procedimiento inaceptable teóricamente por los graves inconvenientes que pudiera originar e impracticable en España con arreglo a su legislación, de acuerdo con ésta, no cabe otro sistema que la solicitud individual para examinar separadamente las circunstancias de cada aspirante y otorgar la concesión mediante los requisitos exigidos por los artículos 25 del Código civil y 101 de la ley del Registro civil.

No es de presumir que la aplicación de estos preceptos legales pueda constituir en todos los casos la dificultad prevista que ahora se trata de remediar en lo posible, toda vez que es de esperar que para la obtención de la ciudadanía de una manera definitiva y legal no vacilen los beneficiados en realizar su viaje a España a fin de hacer la manifestación a que dichos artículos se contraen de renunciar a toda otra nacionalidad y para jurar la Constitución de la Monarquía. Pero las circunstancias especiales a que antes se ha hecho referencia con relación a los individuos de que se trata, pueden justificar la imposibilidad—siempre que sea alegada en los términos hábiles que al efecto se establecerán—para que aquéllos se trasladen a España; y siendo esto así, debidamente comprobado, no puede haber inconveniente (ya que no ha de pugnar con la ley ni alterar sustancialmente sus preceptos) en aplicar a esos casos, por analogía, lo dispuesto en el artículo 19 del Código civil, que al conceder a los hijos de extranjeros, nacidos en España, la facultad de optar por la nacionalidad española cuando lleguen a la mayor edad, les autoriza, si residen en el extranjero, para hacer esta manifestación ante los Agentes diplomáticos y consulares del Gobierno español. Y para el fin indicado, se hace la adaptación consiguiente de los citados artículos, que si bien obedecen a la necesidad—apreciada como supuesto substantivo y basada en una doble consideración política y sentimental—de que el extranjero tome posesión real de la ciudadanía es-

pañola en territorio español que lo sea por su propia naturaleza y no por una ficción de territorialidad, son también expresión de un precepto adjetivo de cuya observancia se declaran exceptuados aquellos casos en que, por claros motivos étnicos e históricos de larga convivencia, se presume vehementemente una como posesión anterior, no pérdida de la cualidad de nacional, y en que, por lo mismo, representa la naturalización menos una concesión propiamente dicha que el reconocimiento de una realidad ya existente. Así nunca podrá considerarse arbitrario que los que obtengan carta de naturaleza con la facultad de su inscripción en los Registros diplomáticos y consulares gocen de la plena nacionalidad española con los derechos y obligaciones a ella inherentes. Pero si esta concesión ha de ser equitativa, no constituyendo un régimen de excepción, ha de tener un término para cuando desaparezcan las causas que la han motivado, por lo cual el plazo que se fija es lo suficientemente amplio y con la condición absoluta de que los que dentro del mismo no hayan obtenido carta de naturaleza, de acuerdo con este Decreto, quedarán sujetos a la legislación vigente para la adquisición de nuestra nacionalidad y no podrán invocar derecho de protección alguno de España, que les será automáticamente cancelado el 31 de Diciembre de 1930.

Por las consideraciones expuestas, el Presidente interino del Directorio Militar que suscribe, de acuerdo con éste, tiene la honra de someter a la sanción de V. M. el siguiente proyecto de Decreto.

Madrid, 20 de Diciembre de 1924.

SEÑOR:

A. L. R. P. de V. M.,
ANTONIO MAGAZ Y PERSA.

REAL DECRETO

A propuesta del Presidente interino del Directorio Militar y de acuerdo con éste,

Vengo en decretar lo siguiente:

Artículo 1.º Los individuos de origen español que vienen siendo protegidos como si fuesen españoles por los Agentes de España en el extranjero, podrán promover hasta el término del plazo, que improrrogablemente finará en 31 de Diciembre de 1930, el expediente en la forma acostumbrada para la petición de carta de naturaleza y en el mismo, además de los requisitos demostrativos de la

circunstancias antes expresadas, se tendrá en cuenta los relativos a la ausencia de cualidades negativas para alcanzar la gracia.

Cuando se haga la solicitud correspondiente diciendo que el peticionario no va a fijar su residencia en España, y alegue al mismo tiempo motivos que le impiden cumplir el requisito que para este caso exige la ley, podrán obtener la dispensa de su viaje a España para realizar la inscripción de la carta de naturaleza, y entonces, la que verifiquen en los Registros diplomáticos y consulares producirá todos los efectos para el pleno disfrute de la nacionalidad española.

Artículo 2.º Dentro del plazo y condiciones fijados en el artículo anterior, se entenderá aclarado el sentido del artículo 25 del Código civil y modificado el artículo 101 de la ley de Registro civil, para que la declaración, renuncia y correspondiente inscripción de los individuos beneficiados por este Decreto que no fijen su residencia en España sea válida cuando se haga en los Registros diplomáticos y consulares.

Podrán así realizarla todos los interesados ante el Agente del punto más próximo, y éste inscribirá el acta en el Registro de que esté encargado, remitiendo copia a la Dirección del ramo para que repita la inscripción en su Registro. A los mismos efectos se entenderá ampliado con un sexto párrafo el artículo 6.º de la ley de Registro civil, que enumera los actos inscribibles en los Registros diplomáticos y consulares.

Artículo 3.º Expirado el plazo improrrogable, que termina en 31 de Diciembre de 1930, los individuos que en el transcurso del mismo no hubiesen pedido la carta de naturaleza aprovechando las condiciones y requisitos mínimos mencionados en el artículo 1.º, dejarán de tener la consideración de protegidos, cualquiera que sea el fundamento que para ello aleguen, y no podrán invocar en lo futuro excepción alguna en la aplicación de las disposiciones vigentes en materia de nacionalidad. Las Autoridades diplomáticas y consulares de España no expedirán por ningún concepto, pasado dicho plazo, certificado alguno relacionado con protección que no esté expresamente reconocida como válida por las Naciones en que ese derecho pueda ser ejercitado auterizadamente.

Artículo 4.º Por los Ministerios de Estado y Gracia y Justicia se dictarán las disposiciones necesarias para

llevar a cumplimiento este Decreto, y por el de la Gobernación se darán las instrucciones precisas en lo que se refiere a la aplicación del artículo 1.º

Dado en Palacio a veinte de Diciembre de mil novecientos veinticuatro.

ALFONSO

El Presidente Interino del Directorio Militar,
ANTONIO MAGAZ Y PERS.

B. Recent Historiography

The reason [cause, causation] that compelled me to include some material related to Italian war crimes and Italian war criminals in occupied Greece during World War II is to highlight the conflicting and contradictory image of wartime Italy as a humanitarian occupying force. This is by itself contradictory since, by definition, any occupation cannot be and is not humanitarian – is inherently inhuman, barbaric. Furthermore, this being the image [i.e. that of the humanitarian] that postwar Italy is portraying and propagating ever since the end of the war, the documented historical record is warranted for elucidation.

The material that will be presented is ancillary to the main concern of the original paper, that of the portrayal of Italian Diplomatic Authorities in occupied Thessaloniki as humanitarians vis à vis Jewish Greeks. It is beyond the scope of this update (and not my intention) to proceed to a full analysis of wartime events in occupied Greece regarding Italian forces and their actions and/or if justice was served after the war (which was not!). The citations will fill the gap.

We start with the **Domenikon massacre** in Central Greece (Region of Thessaly) on February 16, 1943⁴. It is interesting to note that it was only in 2009 (66 years later!) that Italy acknowledged her guilt and the Italian Ambassador Gianpaolo Scarante in Athens visited Domenikon to offer the regrets of the Italian State⁵. Three things are interesting: First, the Mayor of

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- 4 The *Domenikon Massacre (La strage di Domenikon)* was a violent reprisal by the Italian Royal Army's 24th Infantry Division Pinerolo during the Axis Occupation of Greece. On 16–17 February 1943, Italian troops executed a total of 175 male civilians from the Domenikon, Mesohori, Amouri and Damasi villages. Domenikon and Mesohori were also set ablaze.
Crimini fascisti, strage di Domenikon, l'Italia chiede scusa alla Grecia (20170825)
https://groups.google.com/forum/#!msg/it.politica.internazionale/tqI45_GwbQ/8EAXuxeM8z8I
<https://drive.google.com/file/d/0B9Aca9qaK9sTZWJrRkJCS1h5b2s/view?usp=sharing>
Le rappresaglie italiane in Grecia, Lettere al direttore, *Giornale di Brescia*, 6 dic 2014
<http://www.giornaledibrescia.it/lettere-al-direttore/le-rappresaglie-italiane-in-grecia-1.1940609> (20170825)
<https://drive.google.com/file/d/0B9Aca9qaK9sTeXV3aG9MdmipiUG8/view?usp=sharing>
Virgilio Ilari, *I crimini di guerra e l'immagine internazionale dell'Italia*, *Conference and Volume Fondo H8*, Crimini di guerra, 16 pp, Leone Editore, January 2014 (see page 7) (20170904)
<https://doi.org/10.13140/2.1.3333.5686>
<https://drive.google.com/file/d/0B9Aca9qaK9sTUVBTVG5ESDRFUF8/view?usp=sharing>
Un Eicidio impunito, *La Nuova Sassari*, 16 febbraio 2009 (20170904)
http://ricerca.gelocal.it/lanuovasardegna/archivio/lanuovasardegna/2009/02/16/SA5PO_SA504.html
<https://drive.google.com/file/d/0B9Aca9qaK9sTVHNVt19xaDVTTWs/view?usp=sharing>
- 5 1943: *l'Italia si scusa per rappresaglia in Grecia* _ *L'ambasciatore d'Italia ad Atene*, Gianpaolo Scarante, *Domenicon_16 Febr 2009*, *storia in rete*, 15 febbraio (20170904)

Domenikon stated, among other, that the *Italians of today are not like the fascists of yesterday*. So the fascists of yesterday were not Italian? Second, the Domenikon visit by the Ambassador came two years after the luxurious edition of *Ebrei di Salonico – 1943, I documenti dell’umanità italiana [Hebrews (Jews) of Thessaloniki – 1943, the documents of Italian humanity]* in 2007. For sure this does not exonerate Italy and it cannot be a positive variable term in an algebraic equation whose result is a quantitative measure of guilt. It is important to remark that not even one perpetrator of the massacre was ever brought to justice, let alone convicted of a crime even though descendants of the victims attempted to bring the criminals to justice⁶. And, third, just a year

<http://www.storiainrete.com/1262/ultime-notizie/litalia-chiede-perdono-per-rappresaglia-in-grecia-nel-1943/>

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/0B9Aca9qaK9sTYkVYc0o0bHQxd0k/view?usp=sharing>

- 6 *Efstathios Psomiadis, Private Communication* (20170904), President of the Society of Families of Victims of the Domenikon massacre. In 2001, they registered a complaint–charge (they sued) with the Office of the Public Prosecutor at the Court of First Penal Instance of Larissa against various Italian Officers of the time. Still pending.

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/0B9Aca9qaK9sTZXE3X1dnM3hQSUU/view?usp=sharing>

before the Italian pardon at Domenikon (2008), the incriminating Espresso article appeared⁷.

Also, in October 2011, a motion was filed with the Military Prosecutor in Italy, still pending

PROCURA MILITARE DELLA REPUBBLICA
presso il TRIBUNALE MILITARE di ROMA
Ufficio Coordinamento Attività di Polizia Giudiziaria
Sez. Crimini di Guerra
Viale delle Milizie n°5/c - 00192 - Roma
(☎ 0039 06 47352922; ☎ 0039 06 3600800)
procurmi.segret@giustizia.militare.difesa.it

OGGETTO:- Ricezione denuncia brevi manu portata da:

- **PSOMIADIS Efstatios** nato a Stefanovuno di Ellassona (GRECIA) il 01.04.1961 identificato mezzo Carta d'Identità n. AI290526 rilasciata dalle località autorità il 22.06.2010, residente in Crisostomu Smirmis, 10, Ellassona - Larissa (GRECIA), e-mail: stapso@sch.gr, cell. 0030-6977356789, tel. 00302493024477.

Il giorno 04 ottobre 2011 alle ore 13:05 negli uffici di questa sezione crimini di guerra della Procura Militare della Repubblica di Roma davanti a noi sottoscritti Ufficiali di P.G. Mar. Ca. Francesco TRIVELLI, Mar. Ord. Annalisa DURANTE e Mar. Ilaria POLLA in servizio presso il reparto in epigrafe danno atto che:

“Alle precedenti ore 12:30 è giunto, presso questa Procura Militare, il nominato in oggetto unitamente a sua figlia PSOMIADOY Venetia nata il 23.07.1994 a Thessaloniki (GRECIA) identificata tramite Carta d'Identità n. AH 267013 rilasciata dalle locali Autorità il 03 luglio 2008, il quale consegna brevi manu una denuncia composta da n. 07 pagine (solo fronte) dattiloscritte in lingua italiana e sottoscritte dal nominato in oggetto, un allegato di pagine n. 10 (solo fronte) in lingua italiana avente come oggetto “Fatti d’arme di Domenikon” datato 23 febbraio 1943, una lista di nomi edita dalla commissione crimini di guerra delle Nazioni Unite nel 1946 riportante due nomi dei soldati italiani ritenuti autori della strage ed un allegato in lingua greca di pagine n. 10 (fronte - retro) riguardanti la delega conferita dai familiari delle vittime del massacro del Domenikon al PSOMIADIS. Per altro fornisco un file power-point con le foto delle vittime, di Domenikon oggi e del tempo, del sacrario, alcune foto di stralci di giornali italiani e foto estrapolate da un filmato dell’epoca girato dalle truppe inglesi dopo la distruzione del villaggio, e foto di conferenze ed eventi tenutisi in ricordo del tragico evento. Si da atto che il PSOMIADIS non parla la lingua italiana e perciò si è avvalso, per la consegna dei documenti di cui sopra, dell’aiuto della figlia, conoscitrice della lingua inglese.

1

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/0B9Aca9qaK9sTTWxHV3RIUk1vaTg/view?usp=sharing>

Eccidi nazifascisti, dopo settant'anni la Procura di Roma apre un'inchiesta, L'Espresso, 4 aprile 2014 (20170824)

<http://espresso.repubblica.it/attualita/2014/04/04/news/eccidi-nazifascisti-dopo-settant-anni-la-procura-di-roma-apre-un-inchiesta-1.159826>

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/0B9Aca9qaK9sTMm5VemRkT3B0M1E/view?usp=sharing>

7 Grecia 1943: quei fascisti stile SS. Domenikon come Marzabotto. Oltre 150 uomini fucilati per rappresaglia. Ora un documentario alza il velo sulle stragi del nostro esercito. Occultate, di Enrico Arosio, L'Espresso, 28 febbraio 2008

<http://espresso.repubblica.it/visioni/cultura/2008/02/28/news/grecia-1943-quei-fascisti-stile-ss-1.7472> (20170904)

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/0B9Aca9qaK9sTVGkzUy1Cd1A0bzb/view?usp=sharing>

Update and Addenda

We continue with the case of **Giovanni Ravalli**⁸. Lieutenant Giovanni Ravalli took part in the massacre of the Village of **Kleisoura**⁹ in North West Greece on April 5, 1944. He was the only Italian war criminal ever tried and convicted in postwar Greece. After pressures from Italy he was

8 Rory Carroll, *Italy's bloody secret*, The Guardian, 25 June 2001 (20170905)
<https://www.theguardian.com/education/2001/jun/25/artsandhumanities.highereducation>
<https://drive.google.com/file/d/0B9Aca9qaK9sTa2lwdm5rUzhMLUk/view?usp=sharing>

Davide Conti, *Criminali di guerra italiani. Accuse, processi e impunità nel secondo dopoguerra*, 344 pp, Editore: Odradek Edizioni, 2011, Roma
[The first part on Greece is mainly on Giovanni Ravalli], (Italiani brava gente_ La pagina nera dei crimini Italiani di Guerra all'Estero)
http://www.tecalibri.info/C/CONTI-D_criminali.htm (20170904)

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/0B9Aca9qaK9sTSWNHdXFBS3hGTm8/view?usp=sharing>

Chapter 4, *Lethal Trajectories_ Perpetrators from Grafeneck to the Risiera*, pp. 137-171, [citation for Giovanni Ravalli in pp. 155-156], in Susanne Knittel, *The Historical Uncanny_ Disability, Ethnicity, and the Politics of Holocaust Memory*, Fordham University Press, 364 pp, 2014, New York

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/0B9Aca9qaK9sTcHdfVWVjZkxfYVk/view?usp=sharing>

Stelios Pericles Karavis, Chapter 5, *Οι πολιτικές σχέσεις της Ιταλικής Δημοκρατίας με το Βασίλειο της Ελλάδας την περίοδο 1947-1953* [The political relations of the Italian Republic with the Kingdom of Greece during the period 1947-1953], pp. 81-94, **Greece, the West and the Mediterranean_ New Research approaches**, Editorial Care E. Botsiou & John Sakkas, Scientific Supervisor Prof. Nikolaos Marantzidis, University of Macedonia
www.uom.gr, 160 pp, 2015, Thessaloniki [Giovanni Ravalli pp. 83-87 in sub Chapter: *The Italian Criminals of War*] (in Greek)

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/0B9Aca9qaK9sTX3NCZ3BNN0IHV2s/view?usp=sharing>

9 For an exhaustive and thorough description of the Kleisoura massacre see:
Stratos N. Dordanas, *Αντίποινα των γερμανικών αρχών κατοχής στη Μακεδονία (1941-1944) - Reprisals of the german authorities of occupation in Macedonia (1941-1944)*, 848 pp, Doctoral Dissertation, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki www.auth.gr, 2002, Thessaloniki (in Greek)
[Chapter on the Destruction of Kleisoura, pp. 543-598]

<http://thesis.ekt.gr/thesisBookReader/id/20569#page/1/mode/2up> (20170905)

<https://phdtheses.ekt.gr/eadd/handle/10442/20569?locale=en> (20170905)

<http://oladeka.com/2016/04/5-%CE%B1%CF%80%CF%81%CE%B9%CE%BB%CE%AF%CE%BF%CF%85-1944-%CE%B7-%CE%BA%CE%B1%CF%84%CE%B1%CF%83%CF%84%CF%81%CE%BF%CF%86%CE%AE-%CF%84%CE%B7%CF%82-%CE%BA%CE%BB%CE%B5%CE%B9%CF%83%CE%BF%CF%8D%CF%81%CE%B1/> (20170905)

Stratos Dordanas April 5, 1944_ The Destruction of Kleisoura
[Giovanni Ravalli] 60 pages_April 5, 2016.pdf (in Greek)

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/0B9Aca9qaK9sTczV5dFZ6T1JLaUk/view?usp=sharing>

set free to face justice in Italy. The result: He (like many others!)¹⁰ had a long and distinguished career in the Italian Public Sector.

This concludes **B**. For completeness I include some recent works having as subject the Italian War Crimes in occupied Greece and their impunity, and the perception of the Italians vis à vis the Germans of the Deutches Reich as occupiers¹¹.

10 Davide Conti, *Gli uomini di Mussolini _ Prefetti, questori e criminali di guerra dal fascismo alla Repubblica italiana*, Giulio Einaudi Editore s.p.a, 282 pp, 2017, Torino [Giovanni Ravalli pp. 153-159]

Mirella Serri, *Gli uomini del Fascismo riciclati anche se CRIMINALI (La Repubblica senza Memoria)*, *Corriere della Sera SETTE*, pp. 54-55, N.8, 24 febbraio 2017

www.einaudibologna.it/images/Pdf/conti%20corriere.pdf (20170905)

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/0B9Aca9qaK9sTejNYQnNjQ05ZR0k/view?usp=sharing>

11 Filippo Focardi, *Italy's Amnesia over War Guilt: The "Evil Germans" Alibi*, *Mediterranean Quarterly*: Fall 2014, 25:4, pp. 5-26, Meditteranean Affairs Inc., Duke University Press, 2015 (20170901)

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/276250130_Italy%27s_Amnesia_over_War_Guilt_The_Evil_Germans_Alibi

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/0B9Aca9qaK9sTVnRKVnhoT1Rlams/view?usp=sharing>

Jason Leech, *Greek perceptions of the 'good Italian' and 'bad German' from invasion (1940) to the London Agreement (1953)*, 8 pp, presented at the *4th Conference of the European Society of Modern Greek Studies*, Granada, Spain, 9th September 2010

www.eens.org/EENS_congresses/2010/Leech_Jason.pdf (20170901)

<https://kcl.academia.edu/JasonLeech> (20170901)

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/0B9Aca9qaK9sTNIQ3QTFxUkxvb00/view?usp=sharing>

Stelios Pericles Karavis, "*La memoria dei crimini di guerra italiani in Grecia*", pp. 53-83, in Elena Pirazzoli (editor), Curatore: Scuola di Pace di Monte Sole, *Sperimentazioni belliche e provvedimenti di rigore. La memoria dei crimini italiani in Spagna, in Grecia e in Jugoslavia (1936-1945)*, 136 pp, Zikkaron, 2016, Marzabotto

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/0B9Aca9qaK9sTMVFybG1DUi0wNDA/view?usp=sharing>

Paolo Fonzi, *Beyond the Myth of the 'Good Italian'. Recent Trends in the Study of the Italian Occupation of Southeastern Europe during the Second World War*, *Südosteuropa Journal of Politics and Society* _ De Gruyter, volume 65, no. 2, Special Issue on *The second world war in historiography and public debate*, pp. 239-259, 2017, Berlin

As a final annotation, The *Treaties of Peace with Italy* are attached as well as the *1953 London Agreement*¹². It is interesting to point out that even though at the preamble of the Peace Treaty the fact that the Kingdom of Italy was an aggressor state is clearly stated, nonetheless, subsequently, this stain-blemish fades away. Furthermore, especially if the reader is ignorant, he or she can only surmise, with certainty, that Italy was either a victim of Germany and/or a member of the victorious Allies if they read the text of the London Agreement. The incriminating past has vanished (magically or miraculously?).

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- 12 HCPP_1945-Draft Peace Treaty with Italy_01-52 Command 6892
Italy No. 1 (1946), DRAFT PEACE TREATY WITH ITALY, Prepared by the Council of Foreign Ministers, for consideration by the Peace Conference of Twenty-one Nations meeting in Paris on the 29th July, 1946, Presented by the Secretary of State for Foreign Affairs to Parliament by Command of His Majesty, House of Commons Cmd. 6892, 52pp, 1946, London
<https://drive.google.com/file/d/0B9Aca9qaK9sTdmNCeUdDaXE0R2s/view?usp=sharing>
- HCPP_1947-TrSer 50 [1948] Treaty of Peace with Italy_01-500
Treaty Series No. 50 (1948), TREATY OF PEACE WITH ITALY, Paris, 10th February, 1947, Presented by the Secretary of State for Foreign Affairs to Parliament by Command of His Majesty, House of Commons Cmd. 7481, 500 pp, 1948, London
<https://drive.google.com/file/d/0B9Aca9qaK9sTckIxZlBYaUFJUm8/view?usp=sharing>
- HCPP_1947-Italy TrSer No51 Maps Annexed Treaty Peace with Italy_01-99
ITALY, Treaty Series No. 51 (1948), MAPS ANNEXED TO THE TREATY OF PEACE WITH ITALY, PARIS, 10th FEBRUARY, 1947 (IN CONTINUATION OF TREATY SERIES NO. 50 (1948) Cmd. 7481), Presented by the Secretary of State for Foreign Affairs to Parliament by Command of His Majesty, House of Commons Cmd. 7482, 99 pp, 1948, London
<https://drive.google.com/file/d/0B9Aca9qaK9sTZjNIWklVQlpTWDA/view?usp=sharing>
- HCPP_1952-Germany No1_1953_ Agreement on German external debts, London, 27 Febr 1953_01-120
Germany No. 1 (1953), Agreement on German External Debts, London, 27th February, 1953, Presented by the Secretary of State for Foreign Affairs to Parliament by Command of Her Majesty, March 1953, House of Commons Cmd. 8781, 120 pp, 1953, London
<https://drive.google.com/file/d/0B9Aca9qaK9sTalVaZ1RaejFaRG8/view?usp=sharing>

C. Bronze Medals for Valor

During my research for the original paper, I discovered that the Italian Ministry of Defense, in 1948, conferred two bronze medals for valor to the following (I attach both).

- A. To the [Flag of the Military Corps of Engineers](#) for valor at the Albanian - Greek front displayed in 28 October 1940
37 - Brevetto di concessione della Medaglia di Bronzo al Valor Militare alla Bandiera dell'Arma del Genio. (Fronte albanico-greco, 28 ottobre 1940) and
- B. To the [Alpine Division "Julia"](#) again for valor.
35 - Brevetto di concessione della Medaglia di Bronzo al Valor Militare al III Battaglione Misto Genio «Julia». (Fronte greco, 5 novembre 1940-23 aprile 1941)
(Bear in mind that my father fought in this war and was lightly wounded).

Just stating the facts, the situation that we are confronted with is the following: The **Italian Republic**, the successor of the aggressor, The **Kingdom of Italy**, who was beaten at the front by the Greek Army, the first defeat of an Axis Power, and also one of the final losers of the World War II, [The Italian Republic] confers medals for valor. And it confers medals of valor to the Italian military who took part in an aggressive campaign – the Italian – Greek War of 1940-1941 – against Greece. This event rendered Italy an indirect culprit of the Holocaust in Greece, a catalyst: As said, Italy was defeated at the front and pushed back (more than 11000 Jewish Greeks soldiers were fighting in Albania). For that reason the Deutsches Reich came to her rescue and invaded Greece. The rest is History.

I started publishing the Certificates of the Bronze Medals for Valor which were posted in the following web site:

<http://www.iscag.it/> and one certificate (Bandiera del Genio) had as download link:

http://www.iscag.it/FOTO/Foto%20Pres%20Generali/Foto%20Bandiera%20Genio/Band_034.jpg

However, at one point, the links were dead. Mind you, those certificates are public domain.

I contacted the Italian Military Attaché in Athens [August 2016]¹³ and they were reinstated. However, on May 2017 they were completely down again, <http://www.iscag.it/> led to:

¹³ Electronic Correspondence with the Military Attaché of the Italian Embassy in Athens, 2016

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/0B9Aca9qaK9sTdjltVWNIRGFCWWc/view?usp=sharing>

<http://www.iscag.it/lacori%20in%20corso.htm> (most probably in their haste to shut it down they misspelled lavori with lacori!) [Unfortunately I did not take a snapshot]. Now www.iscag.it has completely disappeared. For your records I attach a pdf snapshot of the site before shutdown¹⁴.

On the other hand, if you go to this site:

<http://www.angetitalia.it/Comando%20Genio-Bandiera-Med-10.htm>¹⁵ (20170903) you get the *Medaglia di Bronzo al Valor Militare concessa all'Arma del Genio*.

It (the site) gives no documents but still on the right side it continues to state the following:

ANGET

**Associazione Nazionale Genieri
e Transmettitori d'Italia**

**Medaglia di Bronzo al Valor Militare concessa
all'Arma del Genio.**

“Durante l'intera Campagna Italo-Greca, in territorio impervio e tra ogni più dura avversità di elementi, ancora una volta tenace, infaticabile, eroica èer spirito di sacrificio e di abnegazione e per appassionata dedizione, assolveva in pieno tutti i compiti, combatteva tra i fanti. A nessuna seconda per audacia per indomito valore, per fervore di energie, di opere, di sacrifici: esempio e promessa di glorie sempre maggiori”.

(Fronte Greco-Albanese, 28 ottobre 1940)

An explanation was offered by an Italian Professor at a conference for these conferral of certificates and medals: He offered as a possible reason that, at the time, due to the communist danger (sic) the Italian state turned a blind eye and conferred the above.

The conclusions are yours.

¹⁴ *Instituto Storico e di Cultura dell'Arma del Genio* [ISCAG]

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/0B9Aca9qaK9sTWkh4c3owWWNIU2c/view?usp=sharing>

Using the feature of archive.org the *WayBackMachine*, I was able to retrieve the following 3 snapshots of www.iscag.it at 3 different dates: (20170825)

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/0B9Aca9qaK9sTa1ZNV1Y5eVJzWVWk/view?usp=sharing>

¹⁵ *ANGET, Associazione Nazionale Genieri e Transmettitori d'Italia*, Medaglia di Bronzo al Valor Militare concessa all'Arma del Genio (20170817)

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/0B9Aca9qaK9sTb3o2d2RyQVFKdlU/view?usp=sharing>

37 - Brevetto di concessione della Medaglia di Bronzo al Valor Militare alla Bandiera dell'Arma del Genio

37 — Brevetto di concessione della Medaglia di Bronzo al Valor Militare alla Bandiera dell'Arma del Genio. (Fronte albano-greco, 28 ottobre 1940)

35 - Brevetto di concessione della Medaglia di Bronzo al Valor Militare
al III Battaglione Misto Genio «Julia»

**35 — Brevetto di concessione della Medaglia di Bronzo al Valor Militare al III
Battaglione Misto Genio «Julia». (Fronte greco, 5 novembre 1940-23
aprile 1941)**

Numero d'Ordine 14006

REPUBBLICA ITALIANA

MINISTERO DELLA DIFESA

Il Presidente della Repubblica

con Suo Decreto in data del 9 Giugno 1948
Visto il Regio Decreto 4 Novembre 1932 n. 1423 e successive modifiche;
Visto il Regio Decreto 23 Ottobre 1942 n. 1495;
Sulla proposta del Ministro Segretario di Stato per gli Affari
della Difesa;
Ha conferito la medaglia di

Bronzo al valor militare
coll'annesso soprassoldo di Lire Trecento annue
alla Bandiera

dell'Arma del Genio

per il III battaglione misto genio della divisione alpina "Julia,"

"Con costante tenacia e brillante genialità, in sei lunghi mesi di guerra, in situazioni ter-
tera criticissime e sotto intenso fuoco di armi nemiche, ha sempre assicurato i collegamenti, ha
costruito ponti e strade, ha preparato apprestamenti difensivi, non esitando, all'occorrenza, a
lasciare gli attrezzi da lavoro e gareggiare con gli alpini nel combattimento."

Fronte greco, 5 novembre 1940 - 23 aprile 1941.

Il Ministro Segretario di Stato per gli Affari della
Difesa rilascia quindi il presente documento per attestare
del conferito onorifico distintivo.

Roma, addì 20 Ottobre 1948

Registrato alla Corte dei Conti
addì 22 giugno 1948
Registo 41 Foglio 18
f.?

Il Ministro
R. Passaroli

Pubbl. nel Boll. Uff. 1948 disp. 24 pag. 2049.

ISTITUTO POLIGRAFICO DELLO STATO

Acknowledgment

I want to thank with appreciation Dr. **Stelios Pericles Karavis** and Dr. **Paolo Fonzi** [Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin, Philosophische Fakultät I, Institut für Geschichtswissenschaften, Südosteuropäische Geschichte, Unter den Linden 6, 10099 Berlin, Deutschland – Germany] for their prompt help, especially their willingness to share with me their recent publications.

*On the occasion of International Holocaust Remembrance Day
and the Conference
“Diplomacy and the deportation of Jews from Macedonia in 1943”,
Her Majesty's Ambassador Charles Garrett and the Minister of Foreign Affairs
of Macedonia Nikola Poposki request the pleasure of the company of*

Mr Paul Haugel

*to a Reception on Tuesday 27 January from 19.00 hrs to 21.00 hrs
at the British Residence, Pitu Guli 31, 1000 Skopje*

*Dress Code
Business*

*RSVP
Arijeta.Hadzi-Hamza@fco.gov.uk*

Please bring this invitation and your ID with you

(From Left to Right)

His Excellency Her Majesty's Ambassador Mr. Charles Garrett
His Excellency The Minister of Foreign Affairs Mr. Nikola Poposki
at the British Residence, Skopje

**On the occasion of the International Holocaust Remembrance Day
and 70 years after the liberation of Auschwitz**

we have the honor to invite you to take part on the

**International Scientific Conference
Diplomacy and the deportation of Jews from Macedonia in 1943**

Skopje, Republic of Macedonia, January 27, 2015, from 9.30 – 16.00

Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the Republic of Macedonia

International Holocaust
Remembrance Alliance - Berlin

Institute of National History

Ministry of Foreign Affairs
of the Republic of Macedonia

Memorial Center of the Holocaust
of the Jews from Macedonia

Diplomatic Club - Skopje

International Holocaust
Remembrance Alliance - Berlin

Institute of National History

Ministry of Foreign Affairs
of the Republic of Macedonia

Memorial Center of the Holocaust
of the Jews from Macedonia

Diplomatic Club - Skopje

International Scientific Conference

Diplomacy and the deportation of Jews from Macedonia in 1943

PROGRAMME

*The goal is to identify and investigate interstate relations that
affected the deportation of Jews from Macedonia and other countries*

Skopje, 27 January 2015
Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the Republic of Macedonia, 9.30 h.

09.30-10.00 Registration of participants

10.00 Official opening of the Conference

Moderator **Jovan Tegovski**, Ambassador, National coordinator for IHRA

- **Nikola Poposki**, Minister for Foreign Affairs of the Republic of Macedonia
- **Dan Oryan**, Ambassador of Israel to Macedonia
- **Pepo Levi**, President of the Board of the Holocaust Fund of the Jews from Macedonia

Introductory remarks by Vlado Kambovski, President of the Macedonian Academy of Sciences and Arts

10.30 – 12.30 First working session: The Deportation and the War

- **Sasko Todorovski** (Skopje): "Collective versus Individual Rights: Repetition of Historical Mistakes"
- **Milan Koljanin** (Belgrade): "Yugoslav Government in Exile and the Holocaust"
- **Todor Cepreganov** (Skopje): "Whether the Party Organization in Macedonia could save the Jews"
- **Paul Hagouel** (Thessaloniki): "The Holocaust of Jewish Greeks and Jews of Thessaloniki: Italian truncated and selective Humanity, Spanish adaptable Citizenship"
- **Maja Susha and Liljana Lazarevska** (Skopje): "Human Relations as a Factor for Rescue and Survival in Difficult Times"
- **Teon Dzingo** (Skopje): "Witnesses' Talk"
- **Gideon Greif** (Tel Aviv): "The Intervention of the German National-Socialist Ministry of Foreign Affairs concerning the Jews in Macedonia, Greece and Bulgaria"
- **Jasminka Namiceva** (Skopje): "Bulgarian Bank – Central Arbiter in the Transfer of the Property of Jews from Macedonia"

Discussions

12.30 Lunch / snack and informal meetings

13.00 – 15.30 Second working session: The International relations and Deportation

Moderator **Goran Sadikarijo**, CEO, Memorial Center of the Holocaust of the Jews from Macedonia

- **Sofija Grandakovska** (Skopje): "Citizenship and the Deportation of the Jews from Macedonia"
- **Lea Cohen** (Geneve): "The Role of the Swiss and the Spanish Embassies in Sofia in March 1943 in Regards of their Efforts to save Lives of Jewish Children"
- **Irena Avirovik** (Skopje): "Italian Diplomacy and the Deportation of the Jews from Macedonia"
- **Nadège Ragaru** (Paris): "The 1945 Trials for antisemitism in Bulgaria:
A Window into Bulgarian-German Relations during World War II"
- **Miso Dokmanovic** (Skopje): "American Diplomacy and the Holocaust"
- **Nicolay Poppetrov** (Sofia): "Secret Diplomacy and Political Circumstances in the Process of taking Decisions for Deportation"
- **Viktor Gaber** (Skopje): "The International Constellations and Rescue of Bulgarian Jews"

Discussions

16.00 Concluding remarks by Dragi Gjeorgiev, Director of the Institute of National History

Languages: English and Macedonian (with simultaneous translation)

Text without citations

The Holocaust of Jewish Greeks and Jews of Thessaloniki: Italian truncated and selective Humanity, Spanish adaptable Citizenship

Paul Isaac Hagouel, Ph.D.

Abstract

The role that Italy played in the Holocaust of the Jews of Thessaloniki has not been documented. Jewish Greeks of Thessaloniki and other nearby locales did not benefit either by Italian or Spanish Diplomacy and the Diplomats. The unfortunate indirect role that Italy played in the Annihilation of Jewish Greeks will be demonstrated. The adaptability, along with the fortunes of war, and, consequently, its interpretation at will by the Spanish Administration, of the Spanish Citizenship (its rights and privileges) of Jewish Thessalonikians is also demonstrated. It is regrettable that the self-evident and obvious duty of a Country – State to protect its own citizens had to be transubstantiated into and elevated to the realm of Humanity and Saving and Rescue.

In the last decade a surge in interest on Holocaust History and Studies worldwide, as well as the maturity of the International Holocaust Remembrance Alliance and its impact on the academic, educational and museums and memorials fields, has produced a corpus of works dealing with many aspects pertinent to the Holocaust. One very noble component is the Rescue of Jews in peril of annihilation during those dark years. Diplomats of various countries played a role in the rescue, some in direct conflict and contrary to the guidelines of their superiors and, many, far exceeding their competence and mandate that entailed personal risk and danger. Events that relate to rescue actions by Spanish Diplomats in Athens and Italian ones in Thessaloniki concerning the Jews of Thessaloniki have been documented albeit lacking in detail, especially for Italy. Italy was an aggressor and perpetrator of crimes, so how can one talk, at the same instance, about Italian humanity? And what sort of citizenship was the Spanish one held by a number of Jews, permanent residents of Thessaloniki, that forbade its holder to enter and take up residence in that same State?

In a previous work of mine I gave the definition of Holocaust where I noted, in particular, that the term Holocaust incorporates all the primal causes, *causae causans*, irrespective of how far back we have to look and trace the past. Any actions or failures to react of any individual, group, society and/or states which tolerate or, worse, kindle activities that may lead to other Holocausts, not necessarily of Jews, are also included in the definition. Consequently we have to trace how Greece found itself

occupied by the Deutsches [German] Reich, the Kingdom of Italy and the Kingdom of Bulgaria in the first place and, thus, the Jews found themselves in this dire predicament with the horrendous outcome and end.

Greece had declared its neutrality early on when the clouds of the impending war were gathering all over Europe. Unfortunately the Head of the Government of the Kingdom of Italy Benito Mussolini had grandiose ambitions about a new Italian Empire in the Mediterranean. Italy tried to provoke Greece with the torpedoing of the cruiser Elli on August 15, 1940. Even though the identity of the perpetrator was correctly presumed (markings on a stray torpedo that hit the breakwater jetty), the Greek Government restrained itself. But, then, Mussolini started getting very restive since he yearned desperately to “match” the war campaign successes and conquests of his ally Hitler. Documents prove that, even if he was not preparing for a campaign against Greece many months in advance, he was considering and planning for it a long time ago. The Reich not only knew about this but was also proactively “advising” and recommending to the Greek Government to come to an agreement with and cede to any eventual demands by their ally Italy who considered the Mediterranean as its sphere of interest and thus [the Reich] was not interested!

With the benefit of hindsight and interpretative synthesis of the facts [correlation of data] I deduce that if Italy hadn't attacked Greece (and without any provocation!) and Greece wouldn't have beaten her back, then Hitler would not have been compelled to come to her rescue and would not have invaded and occupied Greece. At 3:00 AM in the morning of October 28, 1940, the Italian Minister to Greece, Emanuele Grazzi, handed an ultimatum to Prime Minister Metaxas demanding free passage of Italian Troops. Metaxas replied with a No and war was de facto declared and hostilities started at the Albanian – Greek frontier. More than 11000 Jewish Greek soldiers were amongst the Greek troops that took part in the campaign, including my father Leon, a Lance Corporal. Greeks dealt the first defeat to an Axis power. Mussolini was humiliated. Understandably Greece invited Britain to assist and British troops landed in Greece. Hitler used this as an additional pretext and on April 6th, 1941 invaded Greece from Bulgaria, an Axis ally. Thessaloniki was occupied on April 9th, 1941.

The conqueror divided Greece into three occupation zones: The Italian one comprising most of continental Greece and many islands, the Bulgarian one comprising Eastern Macedonia and Thrace except the

border zone with Turkey, and the German one with the rest of the territory which included also Thessaloniki and its vicinity.

Before we proceed, the term Jew in Greece should be clarified. From the first ever temporary Constitution of Epidavros in 1822, the 3d Protocol of the Treaties of London in 1830, and with all successive Constitutions to this day, Greece was founded as a State recognizing only Hellenes and no minorities. All religions were/are tolerated and all were/are fully emancipated. All Hellenes have Civil Rights, there exist no Group Rights. After the conclusion of the Balkan Wars, Thessaloniki became officially Greek with the 1913 Treaty of Bucharest. All its inhabitants, Christians, Muslims, Jews, Armenians etc became Greek – Hellenes with the 1913 Treaty of Athens.

Hence, on April 9th, 1941, the Jewish population of Thessaloniki is comprised, overwhelmingly, by Jewish Greeks. There exist around five hundred Jewish Spaniards, permanent residents of Thessaloniki and a lesser number of Jewish Italians [note that in the Italian Diplomatic Correspondence they are referred as *Israeliti Italiani* i.e. *Italian Jews*], also permanent residents of Thessaloniki, and a minute number of Jews of various other nationalities. It is more than safe to claim that the totality were of Sephardic origin and spoke Ladino [Judeo Espagnol].

The fate of the Jewish Greeks of Thessaloniki as well as of the Bulgarian occupied territories and of the former Italian occupied ones after Italy capitulated on September 8, 1943 was total annihilation in the Death Camps in Poland. A few thousand, who fled and hid or were rescued, survived. Of the 48000 something deported – shipped to Auschwitz – Birkenau from Thessaloniki and surroundings, in the spring on 1943, only 2000 survived the ordeal. The Sephardic Jewish Greeks from Eastern Macedonia and Thrace were also deported and all were annihilated at Treblinka.

In 2007, the Italian Embassy in Athens published a volume titled *Ebrei di Salonicco – 1943, I documenti dell'umanità italiana [Hebrews – Jews of Thessaloniki – 1943, the documents of Italian humanity]*. It is regrettable that Ambassador Gianpaolo Scarante, in his salutation of the edition, only mentions the persecution of the Jews during the Nazi (note: neither German nor Italian) occupation and exalts the courageous humanity demonstrated by many Italians in Greece without further elaboration. Bear in mind that during the same chronological period atrocities were committed by the Royal Italian Army against civilians and Greeks were literally dying of hunger due to the occupation policies of the Axis allies

and of the onerous financial burden of compulsory occupation costs decided and signed by the Reich and the Italian Kingdom in Rome. It is of interest to put the historic record, regarding Italy and the Jews of Thessaloniki during World War II, in its true context and frame.

Even though Italy was an aggressor and occupier of Greece, she was never prosecuted nor indicted in the Nuremberg trial. But Italy was also a perpetrator of crimes of war and crimes against humanity. Italy was a de facto dictatorship tolerated by the King and there existed a benign relationship between the Italian State and the Vatican. Italy had already committed crimes in Ethiopia and, concerning Jews, passed Anti-Judaic Laws starting in 1938, which were not even rescinded during the brief period of the Badoglio Administration till the capitulation. Furthermore, all the Italian Diplomats in Greece have not been on record as opposing the regime and what it represented. Continuing to serve can only be construed as tacit approval of the policies of their government.

Actually, surmising from Italian Diplomatic Documents as presented in both the publication of the Italian Embassy and Daniel Carpi's work titled *Italian Diplomatic Documents of the History of the Holocaust in Greece (1941–1943)* (which, in itself, is another misleading title with respect to its contents), Consuls Guelfo Zamboni and his successor, after June 18, 1943, Giuseppe Michele Mario Castruccio along with Captain Lucillo Merci managed to protect around 350 Jews of Thessaloniki who were either Italians or had a connection with Italy and so they could provide them with temporary Italian citizenship documents. (These events were taking place, during the first half of 1943, when Adolf Eichmann's emissaries were busy deporting all the Jewish Greeks to Auschwitz – Birkenau). As I noted above, those were considered first Jews and then Italians, thus being lesser Italians than the non-Jews. Still, the documents and the numbers reveal, beyond any reasonable doubt, that the Diplomats and the Captain protected, shielded and saved citizens of their Country as was their duty, albeit of Jewish religious descent, and not just any Jew. Granted, they showed zeal in this endeavor; however, they never veered out of their diplomatic competence. They never reached out to Jewish Hellenes to distribute something close to Schutz-Pässe as Swede Raoul Wallenberg and Swiss Carl Lutz handed out in the thousands in Budapest to Jewish Hungarians facing imminent fatal danger, a year later, in 1944. And, furthermore, displaying [personal] courage means that we face danger. I do not see or discern that the aforementioned [Italian] diplomats were facing any real danger to their safety with their actions which were completely within their bounds. Still it was an attainment of humanitarian deed even if it was limited in its scope.

In my humble opinion and, in the name of the truth, the title should not be *Hebrews of Thessaloniki*. The correct, and precise one, has to be ***Jewish Italians of Thessaloniki***. Furthermore, we read in the Italian Press that Zamboni is portrayed both as the Italian *Schindler* and/or the (Giorgio) Perlasca of Thessaloniki [*il Perlasca di Salonicco*]. How I long-wish that this was really true!

And it did not – does not do justice to Democratic Post War Italy that the Italian Ministry of Defense conferred, in 1948, the Bronze Medal for valor (sic) to the Flag of the Corps of Engineers (of the Italian Army) respecting the whole “Italian – Greek campaign” at *Fronte Albano – Greco, 28 Ottobre 1940*! And, even more damaging, in the year 2012, Ercole Viri, Mayor of Affile, defended a decision by the City Council to use 130000 € of public funds in order to honour convicted war criminal Field Marshal Rodolfo Graziani with a mausoleum and memorial park! I yearn to feel confident that the Ancient Greek adage of Demosthenes *προς γαρ το τελευταίον εκβάν έκαστον των πριν υπαρζάντων κρίνεται* (*all previous events are judged according to the last one*) does not hold true in this case.

Italy has to come to terms with some of her rather shameful and ignoble deeds of her past that shade her otherwise postwar stellar record. The cultivation of the notion of the “good” Italian versus the “bad” German and of their depiction as saviors of Jews in general, is being questioned, albeit belatedly and slowly. Historiography always has the last word.

Another special group of non-Greek nationals Jewish inhabitants of Thessaloniki was that of the Spanish nationals, around 500 strong. These were Spanish citizens but they were not allowed to enter Spain automatically. They had to renew their Certificate of Nationality each year (see Figures 1 & 2). The Certificate was issued by the Spanish Consulate of Thessaloniki. As a group they were exempt from the racial laws that were applied to their Jewish Greek coreligionists and fellow Sephardim, i.e. they did not have to wear the Yellow Star or live in the Ghetto. Spain was a neutral country albeit favorably predisposed towards the German Reich and the Axis Powers. General Franco was the Leader of the State and the Monarchy had been abolished.

As long as Spain was both neutral and friendly towards Germany, Jewish Spaniards were relatively safe. However, with the tempo of the sequence persecutions – deportations accelerating in 1943, the German appetite for

more Jews to destine for “Special Treatment [Sonderbehandlung]” increased. Spain’s reluctance to accept large numbers of its undesirable non–resident citizens risked to be construed by the Germans as a «carte blanche» to do as they please with the Jewish Spanish nationals in its fold. Nevertheless, after much bureaucratic deliberation among the pertinent German and Spanish Authorities, the Germans finally deported the Spanish nationals to Bergen–Belsen [August 2, 1943] and housed them in separate barracks. After further deliberations among the Spanish Government and the Germans they were finally freed and allowed to travel to and enter Spain via France (all 367 of them). Their sojourn in Spain was brief, just a few months in Barcelona, and then they were shipped to Casablanca on June 14, 1944. With the assistance of UNRRA they were sent to Palestine. They were finally able to return to Greece after August 9, 1945 . All these events are documented via the Certificates of Nationality and the Family (couple) Spanish Passport of David Jacob Gattegno and Rachel Gattegno in my possession. (See the Addendum in the end of the paper)

What makes this topic more pressing today is the need to set the record straight as was/is the case of wartime Italy. Starting with year 2008, the first edition of the book by Matilde Morcillo Rosillo and titled *Sebastián de Romero Radigales y los Sefardíes de Grecia (1943 – 1946)* [*S. R Radigales and the Sephardic (Jews) of Greece (1943 – 1946)*] is published. The editor is Casa Sefarad Israel, Madrid. The cover shows people wearing the Yellow Star of David and all pages of the book carry this Holocaust ubiquitous symbol. Yet, Jewish Spaniards were exempt in being marked. In the Preface, the then Spanish Minister of Foreign Affairs Miguel Ángel Moratinos repeats the title and compliments the work of Rosillo for her “*documented exposition of the saga of those Spaniards*”. However, in the Greek translation, the title is translated as *Spain and the Jews of Thessaloniki 1943 – 1950 (!?)* (I am curious; did the Ministry check the translation?). Thus Sephardi is equated to Jew and vice versa.

Guessing from the title one might infer that Radigales was somehow involved with ALL the Sephardi Jews of Greece – I wish he was! Then, in the third page, a more extended title is given that puts the matter in a correct perspective: *Sebastián de Romero Radigales y Los Sefardíes Españoles de Grecia Durante El Holocausto a Través de La Correspondencia Diplomática* [*Radigales and the Spanish Sephardim of Greece during the Holocaust through Diplomatic Correspondence*]. This secondary title reveals that Radigales was either interested or, most probably, could shield and protect only Sephardic Jews holding the

Spanish citizenship and not the rest of the Sephardim (By the way, Greece was also home to non – Sephardic communities such as the oldest **Romaniote** community, numbering almost 2000 souls, at Ioannina (Janina) – of the 1960 deported to Auschwitz in March, 25, 1944, 1850 would never return).

The case of the Jewish Spaniards in Thessaloniki is more peculiar than the one of the Jewish Italians. Spain was neutral; no Anti-Judaic Laws were passed even though Anti-Semitism was existent even among some of Franco's closest advisors and/or associates and collaborators. Hence one would expect that the self evident duty of the Spanish Legations, present in countries occupied by the Reich, would be to do their utmost to protect and shield their citizens from any perceived dangers. And, yet, this obvious obligation was not transubstantiated into proactivity and action. However, if we take into consideration that Franco remained, for his own reasons, both a believer of and a fancier for Hitler to deliver an Axis victory instead of him (Franco) being a reasoner, and that he did not break off diplomatic relations with the Großdeutsches Reich until May 8th, 1945, VE Day, then we should not be surprised about the vacillations of Spanish Diplomacy vis à vis its own citizens, albeit of Jewish descent, as well as the peculiar adaptability of the rights and/or privileges of that citizenship to the whims of who knows which advisor or confidant of Franco, in 1943 and 1944.

Again, I emphasize that Radigales, who arrived in Athens on April 1943, like Zamboni, acted within his competence, albeit pressuring his government to take action in repatriating its citizens of Jewish religious descent. He is supposed to have stated that, if the Spanish government did nothing to protect its citizens, Spain would incur the wrath of the Allies and not only. If nothing else, he was speaking in logic and realism that also sprang by the obvious change of the fortunes of war against the Axis powers ever since the surrender of Field Marshal Paulus' 6th Army in Stalingrad on February 1st, 1943. Final defeat of the Reich loomed unmistakable.

It seems that the evident imminent collapse of the German Reich a year later (1944) might have made a noticeable difference in compelling, driving and/or nudging governments and/or their envoys to take action. This was most apparent in Budapest. It is there that the daring Italian Giorgio Perlasca, in conjunction with the activities of Diplomat Ángel Sanz-Briz, Head of the Spanish Legation, acted against inhumanity. First Ángel Sanz-Briz got authorization from the Spanish Government to grant Spanish citizenship to Sephardim in Budapest based on and applying the

1924 Royal Law for granting citizenship to people Sephardic origin. However, he was not able to find more than 45 Sephardim amongst the hundreds of thousand of Ashkenazim. He was authorized to provide protection, and hence citizenship for up to 200. So the 200 documents were multiplied and the serial numbering was always the same. Perlasca continued the work after Sanz-Briz was ordered to leave Budapest by daringly assuming the role of continuator in the stead of Sanz-Briz. Now imagine what the turn of events could have been for the Sephardim Greeks of Thessaloniki if the Spanish Legation in Athens had also extended such protection.

For completeness I am quoting 2 recent publications: First the joint 2008 bilingual publication of the Spanish Ministry of Foreign Affairs and Casa Sefarad titled *Visas for Freedom – Spanish Diplomats and the Holocaust*. Pages 40 to 47 of the document in pdf format are devoted to the efforts of Radigales for the repatriation of the Jewish Spaniards. It is interesting to indicate that on page 14 (second page of pdf) of the promotional flyer for the exhibition it states (in Spanish) that Radigales made efforts to repatriate the Sephardim, without distinguishing between the Greek ones, the overwhelming majority, and the Spanish ones, the minute minority.

On November 2014, a 44 page publication of the Spanish Ministry of Foreign Affairs (in Spanish) appears titled *MÁS ALLÁ DEL DEBER, La respuesta humanitaria del Servicio Exterior frente al Holocausto* [*Beyond the Call of Duty, Humanitarian response of the Foreign Service to the Holocaust*]. Pages 13 and 14 are dedicated to Radigales and his actions while in Athens.

Italy and Spain today are far removed from their respective pasts. Spain should be complimented for her earnest efforts in the last 20 years to reach out to all its Sephardic descendants via Casa Sefarad and with its biennial World Gathering for Erensyia Sefaradi, and the new Citizenship Law. Italy is, understandably, proud of acts of humanity during the war albeit truncated and selective and carried out by individuals at their own initiative and not as a state policy. Slowly she is coming to terms with her recent history.

Nevertheless, the best would have been for us not to be here today to commemorate tragic events. I am sure (I hope!) this history will never be repeated.

Thank you

Paul Isaac Hagouel

Brief Curriculum Vitae

I was born in Athens, Greece on March 16, 1950. I received the B.E. “*summa cum laude*” in 1972 [top graduate in the School of Engineering and Science] and the M.S. degree in Electrical Engineering from New York University, in 1973. I received the Ph.D. in Electrical Engineering and Computer Sciences from the University of California, Berkeley in 1976.

My Doctoral Dissertation dealt with the *X-Ray Microfabrication of Blazed Diffraction Gratings*. While at Berkeley, together with Andrew R. Neureuther, I developed and presented the physical and mathematical foundation of the modeling of the etch front advancement process together with a novel algorithm capable of three-dimensional simulation, the Ray Tracing Algorithm. Our work has been the basis, since its presentation, of continuous and ongoing research in front and boundary advancement modeling and simulation (including etching and deposition) worldwide. The research was funded by the US Air Force Office of Scientific Research via a grant by the Joint Services Electronics Program.

I have taught on an adjunct basis at the Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Greece, from 1977 to 1983. I initiated and taught a course on Integrated Circuits, Solid State Theory, and Devices, and Microfabrication and Process Simulation. I also taught Holography as part of a course on Advanced Topics of Physics. I advised many students on Diploma Thesis and graduate students on their Doctoral Dissertations. I was a Visiting Research Engineer with the Electronics Research Laboratory, University of California, Berkeley, from January to August 1995. While there, I engaged in fundamental resist research and also taught a course in the EECS department of the University and advised doctoral candidates. My current research interests center in process modeling and simulation algorithms, resist studies, IC fabrication technology, nanofabrication, and semiconductor device physics. I have published many technical papers in international peer reviewed journals and international pertinent conference proceedings [38 publications], plus lecture notes. I have more than 500 citations of my research work from international researchers. Besides Greek, I am fluent in French and English and adequate in German and Spanish.

I am also interested (amongst others) in the study of History in General, History of Modern Greece, History of Holocaust, Vichy France, Human Rights and Religious Freedoms and Comparative Religious Studies. I have published and lectured extensively, both in Greece and abroad (Philadelphia [USA], Sofia, Skopje and Paris) on the Holocaust in Greece and the Balkans. My works are all uploaded and downloadable from the following site:

{ <http://independent.academia.edu/PaulIsaacHagouel> }

I am a member of Tau Beta Pi, Eta Kappa Nu, and Sigma Xi Honor Societies [Engineering, Electrical Engineering, and Research respectively]. I was an Eta Kappa Nu International Director at its governing board for two years (1982-1983). I am a Member of the Governing Board of the Jewish Museum of Greece, Athens {www.jewishmuseum.gr}. I am a member of the Academic Working Group of the Greek Delegation to the International Holocaust Remembrance Alliance { <http://www.holocaustremembrance.com> }

I am married to Nelly Isoua and have two children Sabrina and Leon.

Thessaloniki, January 2015

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Conference “Diplomacy and the deportation of Jews from Macedonia in 1943”

January 27, 2015 by [kristina](#) in [Macedonia](#)

International scientific conference “Diplomacy and the deportation of Jews from Macedonia in 1943” will be held on the occasion of the International Day of Remembrance of the Holocaust and 70th anniversary of the liberation of Auschwitz.

The conference is organized by the Institute of Natural History, the Holocaust Memorial Center of the Jews from Macedonia and Diplomatic Club – Skopje, and will be opened by the Foreign Minister Nikola Popovski, and about its importance will speak President of the Macedonian Academy of Sciences and Arts Vlado Kambovski.

The conference aims to identify and investigate the relationship between states and conditions that influenced the deportation of Jews from Macedonia and other countries.

In their papers will participate domestic and foreign researchers and experts in this period of history.

The International Alliance for Holocaust Memorial from Berlin in whose activities participate and Macedonia supports the conference.